

1 **Late Pleistocene to modern precipitation changes at the Paranal clay pan, central Atacama**
2 **Desert**

3 Volker Wennrich¹, Christoph Böhm², Dominik Brill³, Rafael Carballeira^{4,5}, Dirk Hoffmeister³, Andrea
4 Jaeschke¹, Florian Kerber⁶, Antonio Maldonado⁷, Simon Matthias May³, Lester Olivares⁸, Stephan
5 Opitz³, Janet Rethemeyer¹, Mark Reyers², Benedikt Ritter¹, Jan H. Schween², Fatma Sevinç¹, Johanna
6 Steiner³, Katharina Walber-Hellmann¹, Martin Melles¹

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8 ¹ University of Cologne, Institute of Geology and Mineralogy, Germany

9 ² University of Cologne, Institute of Geophysics and Meteorology, Germany

10 ³ University of Cologne, Geographical Institute, Germany

11 ⁴ University of A Coruña, Faculty of Science, Spain

12 ⁵ University of Valencia, Institute for Biodiversity and Evolutionary Biology, Spain

13 ⁶ European Southern Observatory, Garching near Munich, Germany

14 ⁷ Centro de Estudios Avanzados en Zonas Aridas, Universidad Católica del Norte, Coquimbo, Chile

15 ⁸ Earth and Atmospheric Sciences, Cornell University, United States

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17

18 **Abstract**

19 The Atacama Desert in Chile is known to be one of the driest deserts on Earth, with dominating hyperaridity at least since the Miocene. During recent times, however, especially the southern part of
20 the Atacama repeatedly experienced exceptional precipitation events, like in 2015 and 2017. Locally,
21 these events with high rainfall rates caused catastrophic floods with significant destruction and human
22 fatalities. Although the meteorological drivers of these heavy rains are widely understood, only little
23 is known about the frequency and amplitude of similar events on geological timescales. Here we present the results of a study on an endorheic clay pan at the southern edge of the hyperarid core of the
24 Atacama, an area with a mean precipitation of approx. 5 mm per year. A modern ground-truthing
25 approach combining sediment data, remote-sensing and meteorological data as well as climate-modelling was applied. Our observations indicate that the clay pan reacted very sensitively to local precipitation
26 during the past 30 years, with four events >20 mm total rain causing sufficient surface run-off
27 in the catchment to partially flood the basin. Comparative analyses of the four events illustrate that
28 the amount of run-off is dependent on the maximum rain rate during the events rather than the total
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32 rain sum. A 1.88-m long sediment core recovered from the centre of the clay pan records the local
33 hydrological and -environmental history since the Late Pleistocene. Sedimentological, mineralogical,
34 geochemical, and biological core analyses imply strong variations in the amplitude of the recorded
35 rainfall, with a clear shift from enhanced alluvial activity caused by higher-amplitude rain events dur-
36 ing the Late Pleistocene to lower-amplitude Holocene events. The Holocene background sedimenta-
37 tion is superimposed by seven severe “Millennial-scale rain events”, which imply precipitation maxima
38 on sub-orbital timescales that are potentially driven by changes in the El Niño Southern Oscillation
39 (ENSO). The results of the study shed new light on the glacial-interglacial but also the sub-orbital pre-
40 cipitation variability in the Coastal Cordillera of the Atacama Desert and its potential driving mecha-
41 nisms, and provide perspectives of the future precipitation development in the region under progres-
42 sive global warming.

43

44 **Keywords**

45 Atacama Desert; Millennial-scale rain events; hyperaridity, clay pan, paleoclimate, precipitation his-
46 tory

47

48 **1. Introduction**

49 With its predominant (hyper-)aridity that dates back to the Oligocene ([Dunai et al., 2005](#)) or Miocene
50 ([Hartley and Chong, 2002](#); [Jordan et al., 2014](#); [Ritter et al., 2018b](#)), the Atacama Desert in northern
51 Chile and southern Peru is known to be one of the oldest and driest deserts on Earth (e.g., [Evenstar et](#)
52 [al., 2017](#)). The extreme aridity, especially in its hyperarid core that receives <2mm of rain per year on
53 average ([Houston, 2006](#)), results from three major driving factors: (1) the long-term stable position of
54 the Atacama at the subsiding branch of the Hadley cell ([Houston, 2006](#)), (2) the rain-shadow effect of
55 the Andes (e.g., [Garreaud et al., 2010](#); [Houston and Hartley, 2003](#); [Rech et al., 2010](#)), and (3) the tem-
56 perature inversion over the coastal Pacific caused by the coastal upwelling of cold Humboldt Current
57 waters ([Garreaud et al., 2010](#); [Garreaud et al., 2009](#)) that effectively prohibit landward moisture
58 transport. The overall arid to hyperarid conditions were, however, repeatedly punctuated by rain
59 events on different timescales. In historical times, extreme precipitation events, like in 1991, 2015, or
60 2022 generated severe floods along the coastal cliff and in parts of the Central Depression, which
61 caused landslides with massive damage and a significant number of human fatalities (e.g., [Bozkurt et](#)
62 [al., 2016](#); [Cabre et al., 2022](#); [de Vries, 2021](#); [Garreaud and Rutilant, 1996](#); [Rondanelli et al., 2019](#);
63 [Vargas et al., 2000](#)). The combination of three main meteorological drivers: (1) El Niño events and an
64 accompanied northward displacement of subtropical troughs ([Houston, 2006](#); [Jara et al., 2022](#); [Ortega](#)
65 [et al., 2019](#); [Vargas et al., 2006](#)), (2) cut-off lows (COL; [Bozkurt et al., 2016](#); [Reyers and Shao, 2019](#)),

66 and (3) moisture conveyor belts (MCB; [Böhm et al., 2021](#); [Reyers et al., 2023](#)) are discussed as poten-
67 tial reasons for extreme precipitation events in the Atacama and validated by climate modelling ex-
68 periments.

69 One of the most extensively investigated rain events in March 2015 with up to 85 mm of precipitation
70 ([Jordan et al., 2020](#)) was caused by the combination of a COL ([Bozkurt et al., 2016](#); [Reyers and Shao,](#)
71 [2019](#)) with a MCB ([Böhm et al., 2021](#)). In contrast to severe floods in the southern Atacama Desert
72 ([Aguilar et al., 2020](#)), the March 2015 event caused only minor surface run-off in the central Atacama
73 ([Jordan et al., 2015](#); [Pfeiffer et al., 2021](#)). Records of historic rain events of the Atacama Desert are,
74 however, scarce, and rarely extend beyond the observation period. In the Antofagasta area, only four
75 heavy rain events were recorded in the 20th century that caused severe debris-flows, with the strong-
76 est events on the 13/06/1940 and the 18/06/1991 recorded with 39 and 42 mm of rain in Antofagasta,
77 respectively ([Pfeiffer et al., 2021](#); [Vargas et al., 2006](#)).

78 On geological timescales, evidences of pluvial phases during the Late Pleistocene are widespread in
79 the Atacama, e.g., in lake sediments ([Grosjean et al., 2001](#); [Pfeiffer et al., 2018](#)), paleowetlands ([Quade](#)
80 [et al., 2008](#); [Sáez et al., 2016](#)); fluvial terraces ([Nester et al., 2007](#); [Rech et al., 2002](#)), coastal alluvial
81 fans ([Vargas et al., 2006](#); [Bartz et al., 2020](#); [Walk et al., 2020](#)), and fossil rodent middens ([de Porras et](#)
82 [al., 2017](#); [Díaz et al., 2012](#); [González-Pinilla et al., 2021](#); [Latorre et al., 2002](#); [Maldonado et al., 2005](#)).
83 Most of these Late Pleistocene archives, however, are influenced by run-off from the Andes, whereas
84 sedimentary archives from the Coastal Cordillera that document solely the rainfall in the desert inter-
85 rior are rather limited (e.g., [Diederich et al., 2020](#); [May et al., 2020](#); [Medialdea et al., 2020](#); [Ritter et](#)
86 [al., 2019](#)). Records of older wet phases beyond the last glacial/interglacial cycle from paleo archives
87 within the interior Atacama are scarce (e.g., [Jordan et al., 2014](#); [Medialdea et al., 2020](#); [Ritter et al.,](#)
88 [2018b](#); [Ritter et al., 2019](#)). Wetter climatic conditions during the Miocene and Pliocene are docu-
89 mented for instance by typical geomorphological features and lacustrine sediment sequences (e.g.,
90 [Bao et al., 2015](#); [Gaupp et al., 1999](#); [Kirk-Lawlor et al., 2013](#); [Ritter et al., 2018a](#); [Ritter et al., 2022](#);
91 [Sáez et al., 2012](#)).

92 Here, we present and discuss the Late Pleistocene and Holocene precipitation history of the Atacama
93 Desert, as reflected in an endorheic clay pan from the southern edge of its hyperarid core. Using a
94 modern ground truthing approach applying remote-sensing and meteorological data as well as climate
95 modelling of the past 30 years, we investigate the sensitivity of the clay pan to historic rain events.
96 Sedimentological, mineralogical, geochemical, and biological data derived from a 1.88 m long sedi-
97 ment core recovered from the centre of the clay pan provide information on the more long-term local
98 paleohydrological and -environmental history. The findings provide a profound understanding of the
99 precipitation-controlled sedimentological, geochemical, and biological processes in the clay pan.

100 2. Site information

101 The Paranal clay pan (PARA_{CP}; 24°29'21"S, 70°08'55"W, 2231 m altitude) is an endorheic lake basin or
102 playa located in the eastern part of the Pampa Remiendos as part of the Coastal Cordillera (Fig. 1).
103 Today, the clay pan forms a terminal basin that is episodically fed by run-off from adjacent alluvial
104 fans and ephemeral streams, which drain a catchment of 170.8 km² that is defined by the up to 3114
105 m high Sierra Vicuña Mackenna mountain range to the northeast, east, and southeast (red polygon in
106 Fig. 1). The endorheic basin was formed when an ESE to WNW-oriented paleochannel system, which
107 formerly drained the Sierra Vicuña Mackenna towards the Pacific Ocean, experienced tectonic block-
108 ing along a trace of the Quebrada Grande Fault System that is part of the Atacama Fault Zone (AFZ;
109 Fig. 1; [Blanco-Arrué et al., 2022](#); [Herve, 1987](#); [Scheuber and Andriessen, 1990](#)). The tectonic activity
110 along the main AFZ is dated to the Middle to Upper Miocene (19 to 5.5 Ma; [Herve, 1987](#)), however,
111 the timing of the tectonic pulse that caused the final blockage of the clay pan is still unknown. Whereas
112 the surrounding mountains are built-up of Jurassic and early Cretaceous dioritic to granodioritic plu-
113 tonic rocks, the playa itself is located in Late Miocene to Pleistocene alluvial to colluvial strata ([Álvarez
114 et al., 2016](#); [Domagala et al., 2016](#)). A geophysical survey studying the sediment geometry of the clay
115 pan using transient electromagnetic (TEM), magnetics, and active seismics predicted two prominent
116 sediment strata with a maximum sediment thickness of 160 ± 10 m in the centre of the basin ([Blanco-
117 Arrué et al., 2022](#)). Based on the results of the geophysical survey, a deep drilling campaign¹ was con-
118 ducted in January/February 2022, which recovered the complete sedimentary infill of the basin down
119 to the bedrock.

120 Gentle slopes in the catchment of the PARA_{CP} exhibit petrogypsic petrosalids soils with indurated gyp-
121 sum crust under a gravel-cover ([Pfeiffer et al., 2021](#)). Locally, boulder fields extend especially at the
122 foot of the surrounding hills. The study area of the Pampa Remiendos and the surrounding mountains
123 is barren of any vegetation except for small niches along fluvial channels, at the flanks of higher moun-
124 tains, and at rocky outcrops ([Díaz et al., 2012](#)). Amongst the few perennial species that survive this
125 harsh environment are *Adesmia atacamensis* Philippi, *Calandrinia salsoloides* Barnéoud, *Cistanthe
126 arancioana* Peralta, *Nolana sessiflora*, and *Cryptantha* sp. ([Elgueta and Barría, 2008](#)).

127 The high elevation and latitudinal position in the southern Atacama have implications on the climate
128 regime of the study region. The inversion height above the nearby Southeast Pacific of about 1000 m
129 ([Muñoz et al., 2011](#)) is mostly below the elevation of the coastal cliff and Coastal Cordillera so that the
130 moisture of the marine boundary layer cannot reach inland. Therefore, moisture advection associated

¹ The scientific core drilling conducted on ESO premises was done under express written permission of ESO and in accordance with Chilean national and local regulations as well as ESO safety rules.

Fig. 1: (A) Color-shaded DEM of the Atacama Desert (derived from SRMT-data, produced by ArcGIS 10.5.1) with isohyets (solid black lines) and the border between winter- and summer-rain dominated areas (after Houston, 2006; dotted black line), showing the locations of the Paranal clay pan ($PARA_{CP}$; red half circle), of the PAG and Huará clay pans (yellow half circles) and of reference records from Saez et al., 2016 (1), Quade et al., 2008 (2), Díaz et al., 2012 (3), Grosjean et al., 2001 (4), Ewing et al., 2008 and Wilhelm, et al., 2008 (5), Knief et al., 2020 (6), and Mörchen et al., 2020 (7). Yellow triangles in red circles mark the positions of the dust samplers with the respective station numbers, black rectangular marks the wider study area in Fig. 1B. (B) Location of the Paranal clay pan in the Pampa Remiendos with the catchment (red polygon) and major tributaries (blue lines) derived from TandemX-DEM. Yellow dots mark the positions of surface samples (from major drainages), the green line the course of the paleo-drainage. Solid, dashed, and dotted black lines highlight observed, inferred and covered faults (modified after Álvarez et al., 2016; Domagala et al., 2016). (C) Close-up of the $PARA_{CP}$ from pansharpned SPOT7 MS imagery (image recovered 26/07/2017) with the position of the PAR-1 coring site and the location of the PAR-22 deep drilling site as well as the Chipana weather station. The yellow dot marks the position of the surface sediment sample of the 2017 rain event.

131 with precipitation is limited to processes, which occur in the free troposphere, such as mid-tropo-
 132 spheric troughs and cutoff lows (Vuille and Ammann, 1997; Marin and Barrett, 2017; Reyers et al.,
 133 2019). These synoptic phenomena emanate from the mid-latitude storm tracks during winter and

134 can reach the southern Atacama Desert. Therefore, the study region is dominated by winter rain (Houston, 2006; Reyers et al., 2021) in contrast to the northern Atacama Desert, which is dominated by
135 summer rain originating from the interior of the continent (Garreaud et al., 2009). Within recent dec-
136 ades the strongest precipitation events in the southern region resulted in up to 60 mm of precipitation
137 within a day (Houston, 2006; Reyers et al., 2021). Seasonal precipitation can be enhanced under El
138 Niño conditions (Houston, 2006; Vargas et al., 2006; Valdés-Pineda et al., 2018). This is attributed to
139 a blocking situation in the midlatitudes that forces low-pressure systems northward (Montecinos and
140 Aceituno, 2003; Vargas et al., 2006). Furthermore, cutoff-low situations are associated with enhanced
141 near-surface relative humidity and changes in the average wind regime (Reyers et al., 2021). Typically,
142 the high insolation of the western Andean slopes leads to strong afternoon westerlies, which force a
143 return flow in upper levels resulting in enhanced subsidence in the coastal desert (Rutllant et al.,
144 2003). At night time, the wind direction reverses. Locally, in the PARA_{CP}, wind velocities exhibit a clear
145 diurnal cycle with low wind from north to northeast in the morning that changes to heavy wind (max.
146 13.2 m s⁻¹) from NW in the afternoon (see Suppl. Fig. S1).
147

148 **3. Material and methods**

149 **3.1. Precipitation data**

150 Continuous precipitation records in the study area are sparse and mainly limited to weather stations
151 in coastal towns, with the stations closest to the Paranal site being located in Taltal (≈110 km), Anto-
152 fagasta (≈120 km), and Aguas Verdes (≈100 km). Precipitation data of these stations are available from
153 the Dirección General de Aguas (DGA; <https://dga.mop.gob.cl/>) and the Explorador Climático of the
154 Center for Climate and Resilience Research (explorador.cr2.cl). The resulting observational gap is pro-
155 gressively filled by fixed and mobile weather stations that were installed within the CRC1211 project
156 (Schween et al., 2020). For instance, a local weather station (S44 “Chipana”; 71°50′52″W, 25°30′46″S),
157 which is equipped with a tipping bucket rain gauge (#52203; Campbell Scientific Ltd.) and a wind mon-
158 itor (#05103; Campbell Scientific Ltd.) was installed in 2021 just outside the Paranal claypan and is
159 continuously recording since 27/11/2021 (Hoffmeister, 2018). Additional precipitation data for the
160 period 16/11/2014-12/02/2019 are available from a LHATPRO microwave radiometer at the ESO VLT
161 observatory installed at Cerro Paranal (PARA_{OBS}; 24°37′S, 70°24′W, 2635m; ≈30 km to the WSW;
162 Kerber et al., 2014). The LHATPRO is equipped with an acoustic Vaisala RAINCAP® Sensor that detects
163 the impact of individual droplets on a ≈9 cm detector disc (Salmi and Ikonen, 2005; Salmi et al., 2005)
164 and provides the rain rate (RR) in mm/h. The RR data were post-processed to correct, e.g., for spurious
165 signals during obvious no rain periods by deleting values constant in time, rain counts occurring at a

166 relative humidity <20.0%, and for outliers deviating more than 4σ from the gliding average. Subse-
167 quently, the cumulative precipitation was calculated by multiplying the RR with the time between
168 individual measurements and adding up the values.

169 To extend the available precipitation time-series and bridge the apparent data gaps, observational
170 data were complemented by simulated precipitation data from a high-resolution regional climate sim-
171 ulation of the Atacama Desert using a Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) model Version 3.9
172 (Skamarock et al., 2008). When driven with reanalysis data, WRF simulations have shown to well re-
173 produce present-day rainfall in the Atacama Desert (Reyers et al., 2021). The WRF model for the pe-
174 riod 1990-2020 (WRF_{era5}) has a 6 km horizontal grid-cell resolution in a domain 26° - 16° S \times 67° - 74° W
175 and was driven by ERA5 global reanalysis data (Hersbach et al., 2018) as initial and boundary condi-
176 tions. Total precipitation data were extracted for the grid cells covering the catchment area of the
177 PARA_{CP} as well as the PARA_{OBS}. Validation of WRF_{era5} data was done through a comparison of daily rain
178 sums for PARA_{OBS} with the LHATPRO data (Suppl. Figs. S2; see supplement for more details).

179 To investigate the frequency of rainfall events at the PARA_{CP} and PARA_{OBS} sites during the Late Pleis-
180 tocene and the Holocene (11-0 ka BP), two additional representative WRF-simulation runs with a hori-
181 zontal resolution of 10 km \times 10 km were analysed for the Last Glacial Maximum (WRF_{LGM}; 21 ka BP)
182 and the historic time interval (WRF_{hist}; Reyers et al., 2023). The WRF-simulation runs were driven by
183 the output of the historical (1990-2014; Jungclaus et al., 2012a) and LGM (Model years 2112-2136;
184 Jungclaus et al., 2012b) experiments of the MPI-ESM-P coupled general circulation model (CGCM;
185 Jungclaus et al., 2013). Frequencies of rain events exceeding certain threshold values (>10 mm; >20
186 mm; >30 mm; >50 mm; >70 mm) within a 25-year time window were calculated for the grid cells of
187 the PARA_{CP} as well the PARA_{OBS}.

188 To evaluate the reproducibility of the rainfall over the PARA_{CP} projected by the MPI-ESM-P GCM-driven
189 model runs, we compared the WRF_{hist} (1990-2020) with the WRF_{era5} (1990-2014) outputs. To match
190 the coarser resolution of the WRF_{hist}, we merged two grid points of the WRF_{era5}. The comparison illus-
191 trates a general agreement of the daily rainfall rates for the predicted rain events at the Paranal site,
192 though with a systematic overestimation of the WRF_{hist} output (Suppl. Fig. S3). Calculated recurrence
193 intervals of >20 mm-events in the WRF_{hist}-model (3.57 years) slightly underestimate WRF_{era5}-derived
194 data. Nonetheless, the MPI-ESM-P GCM-driven WRF_{hist} model appears to suitably simulate the modern
195 climatology.

196

197 **3.2. Field work**

198 Since 2015 the Paranal clay pan was subject of several field campaigns with the aim of validating its
199 suitability as a long-term paleoclimate archive, eventually leading to a scientific deep drilling that was

200 finally conducted in January/February 2022 under the permissions of the Servicio Nacional de Ge-
201 ología y Minería de Chile (SERNAGEOMIN) and the European Organisation for Astronomical Research
202 in the Southern Hemisphere (ESO) and funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (German Re-
203 search Foundation).

204 During a field visit on 15/03/2015 (only 9 days before the March 2015 rain event), a pilot core with a
205 total length of 1.88 m length (PAR-1) was recovered from the western part of the clay pan
206 (24°29'12.92"S, 70° 8'58.93"W; Fig. 1C). Coring was conducted using a hand-held percussion drilling
207 system equipped with a liner core sampler (Eijkelkamp, NL) using opaque plastic liners of 5 cm in di-
208 ameter to avoid light exposure. Additional core-catcher samples that stuck out of the plastic liner were
209 recovered as mixed samples from the lowermost 6 cm of the sampler.

210 Supplementary surface samples for ground truthing of the core data were taken in January 2022 from
211 five major tributaries of the PARAC_p (yellow dots in Fig. 1B) and from the infill of an artificial pit initially
212 dug during a field sampling on 06/04/2015 (Fernandez-Martinez et al., 2019; Fig. 1C; Suppl. Fig. S4),
213 just after the 2015 but prior to the 2017 rain event. Due to the known timing of the digging and its
214 obvious water-transported origin, the sediment infill of the former pit can be directly linked to the
215 subsequent 2017 rain event. For comparison, additional three dust samples were collected using a
216 marble dust collector (MDC; approx. 1.5 m above ground; Goossens and Offer, 2000) at different sites
217 in the Coastal Cordillera next to local weather stations (S12: 21°25'10"S; 69°57'35"W; 695 m asl; S22:
218 19°36'29"S; 70°05'46"W; 1179 m asl; S23: 20°04'25"S; 69°56'06"W; 1151 m asl; Hoffmeister, 2018; Fig.
219 1A). Due to its special design, the MDC preferably receives horizontal dust (Goossens and Offer, 2000).
220 The samples were recovered in February and March 2023, approx. 5 years after installation of the
221 collectors.

222 A high-resolution digital surface model (DSM) of the Paranal clay pan was acquired during a field cam-
223 paign in November 2021 by Unmanned Aerial Vehicle- (UAV) drone imagery. In total 619 aerial images
224 were taken with a DJI Phantom4 (12.4 Mp, 20 mm lens; 35 mm equivalent—Model FC330) at 199 m
225 above ground with 48 mm/pixel ground resolution. Ground control was derived from 10 control points
226 measured with a Trimble R10 RTK-DGPS, resulting in a mean horizontal and vertical error of 116 mm
227 and 27 mm, respectively. Processing of the drone images was conducted with AgiSoft Photoscan Pro-
228 fessional (vers. 1.5.2) and resulted in a DSM with an average pixel resolution of 95 mm and a corre-
229 sponding mean point density of 111 points m⁻².

230

231 3.3. Remote sensing data

232 To investigate the influence of precipitation events on the Paranal clay pan, high-resolution satellite
233 imagery of the PARAC_P area prior and after selected events were investigated. For the most recent
234 events, 3-m resolution multispectral images from PlanetScope (Planet Team, 2017) were comple-
235 mented by Sentinel-2A (10-m resolution), Landsat 7 ETM and 8 OLI (30-m resolution), and SPOT 7 (6-
236 m resolution) images. For the events prior to 2001, only Landsat 5 TM images with a 30-m pixel reso-
237 lution were available. Landsat 7 ETM+ /8 OLI and SPOT 7 images were pansharpened using the pan-
238 chromatic band (band 8 for Landsat 7/8) with the QGIS software package (vers. 3.2.8; QGIS.org 2023)
239 to increase the pixel resolution to 15 and 1.5 m, respectively.

240 The extent of moist areas and open-water ponds within the clay pan was mapped with QGIS using the
241 natural colour band combinations. To validate the visual mapping approach, the Modified Normalized
242 Difference Water Index (MNDWI; Xu, 2006) was calculated in QGIS using the Green and the Short-
243 wave infrared -1 (SWIR₋₁) reflectance bands using the formula:

$$244 \quad \text{MNDWI} = \frac{(\text{Green} - \text{SWIR}_{-1})}{(\text{Green} + \text{SWIR}_{-1})}$$

245 For Landsat 5 TM and Landsat 7 ETM+ images, bands B02 (Green) and B05 (SWIR₋₁), for Landsat 8 OLI
246 bands B03 (Green) and B06 (SWIR₋₁), and for Sentinel-2A bands B03 (Green) and B11 (SWIR₋₁) were
247 selected. The MNDWI has shown to reliably detect open water while effectively reducing noise from
248 built-up land, vegetation, and soil compared to other indices (Xu, 2006; Yan et al., 2017). Threshold
249 values for open-water detection were empirically determined from the MNDWI histograms.

250 Surface areas and volumes of open water bodies were calculated in QGIS using the “Volume Calcula-
251 tion Tool” plugin based upon their mapped aerial extents and the UAV-based DSM.

252

253 3.4. Lab work

254 3.4.1. Core processing and magnetic susceptibility analyses

255 Prior to the opening of the sediment cores in plastic liners, the lowermost parts of the two core sec-
256 tions (PAR1-1 and PAR1-2), corresponding to sediment depths of 1.76-1.84 m and 0.87-0.96 m, re-
257 spectively, were cut for optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) dating. The remaining core liners
258 were cut lengthwise. The magnetic susceptibility (MS) was measured in 1-mm resolution on one core
259 half using a Multi Sensor Core Logger (MSCL, Geotek LTD) equipped with a MS3 meter and a MS2E
260 point sensor (Bartington Instruments Ltd., UK). The other core half was sub-sampled in 2-cm slices,
261 resulting in 89 subsamples, which were subsequently split into aliquots for further analyses. An addi-
262 tional set of ten large-volume bulk sediment samples was taken unevenly-spaced in 6.5-35 cm resolu-
263 tion throughout core PAR-1 for pollen and organic geochemical analyses.

264 3.4.2. Grain-size analyses

265 Granulometric analyses were carried out on aliquots of the 89 regular subsamples from core PAR1
266 and a series of modern analogue samples, namely fluvial sediment samples from PARAC_P tributary
267 channels (n=5), a flood sample of the 2017 rain event (n=1), and dust samples from the Coastal Cor-
268 dillera (n=3). Analyses were performed with a LS13320 laser diffraction particle sizer (Beckman Coulter
269 Inc., USA) for the 0.04-2000 µm grain-size range. For the measurement, approx. 0.5 g of the raw sed-
270 iment was dispersed using sodium pyrophosphate (Na₄P₂O₇, 2.5 g/l) after 1 min ultrasonic treatment.
271 Prior to analyses, gravel was removed by sieving through a 2-mm mesh to avoid clogging of the sys-
272 tem. The gravel content (wt. %) of the total sediment was calculated after drying. Average values of
273 the other grain-size fractions were calculated from four replicate measurements of each sample. Pro-
274 cessing of the raw data was done using the Gradistat software package (Blott and Pye, 2001) according
275 to the geometrical method of Folk and Ward (1957). End-member (EM) modelling of the unprocessed
276 grain-size data was conducted using the Matlab[®]-based software tool AnalySize 1.2.2 (Paterson and
277 Heslop, 2015).

278 3.4.3. Mineralogical and geochemical analyses

279 For the mineralogical and geochemical analyses, approx. 10 g of dry sediment of all 89 regular sub-
280 samples was ground to <63 µm using a planetary mill (Fritsch, Germany). The bulk mineralogy of the
281 samples was analysed by powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) on the homogenized and ground sediment
282 at the Institute of Geoscience, University of Bonn, Germany. Data was acquired using a SIEMENS
283 D5000 θ/θ-diffractometer in Bragg-Brentano geometry, equipped with a point detector and a second-
284 ary graphite monochromator and operated at 40 kV and 40 mA. Scanning was conducted between 4
285 and 70° 2θ with 0.02° steps 2θ and an acquisition time of 2 s per step. The qualitative and semi-quant-
286 itative evaluation of the mineral phases was performed using the EVA V5.1 (Bruker AXS, 2019) and
287 TOPAS V6 software packages (Bruker AXS, 2015), respectively, and the PDF-2 database (Gates-Rector
288 and Blanton, 2019). Only mineral phases with contents >1% were considered.

289 Inorganic elemental concentrations of the 89 core samples were determined by non-destructive en-
290 ergy-dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectrometry (EDXRF) using a SPECTRO XEPOS (SPECTRO Analytical
291 Instruments Ltd., Germany) analyser in a helium gas atmosphere. For the analysis, 5 g of the homog-
292 enized and ground sample aliquot was mixed with 1 g of CEREOX binder Licowax (Fluxana GmbH & Co
293 KG, Germany) and pressed into 32-mm pellets. Element contents from Na to U were analysed simul-
294 taneously, corrected for the specific sample weight, and are presented as average values calculated
295 from two duplicate measurements (standard deviation <5%). The results are complemented by high-
296 resolution elemental analyses, which were conducted by non-destructive X-ray fluorescence (XRF)

297 scanning on the intact archive halves of the core segments using an ITRAX XRF core scanner (Cox An-
298 analytical Systems, Sweden). Scanning with ITRAX was performed at 1-mm resolution using a 1.9 kW Cr
299 tube set to 30 kV and 55 mA.

300 The contents of total carbon (TC), nitrogen (TN), and sulphur (TS) in the 89 core samples were meas-
301 ured by combustion of 5-10 mg sample material in a Vario Micro Cube elemental analyser (Elementar,
302 Germany) as described by [Berg et al. \(2021\)](#). The total organic carbon (TOC) content was calculated
303 from the difference of TC and total inorganic carbon (TIC) content, which were determined with a
304 DimaTOC 2000 elemental analyser (DIMATEC Analysentechnik GmbH, Germany) by combustion of 30-
305 50 mg sample at 900°C (TC) and 160°C (TIC), respectively, the latter after treatment with phosphoric
306 acid (H₃PO₄, 40%).

307 *3.4.4. Statistical analyses of inorganic proxies*

308 To disentangle potential dependencies of the EDXRF-derived element concentrations and to assign
309 potential mineral sources of element variations, we applied a multivariate statistical approach to the
310 concentrations of 24 elements that bear significant signal beyond detection limit (Na, Mg, Al, Si, P, S,
311 Cl, K, Ca, Ti, Mn, Fe, Ni, Cu, Zn, As, Br, Rb, Sr, Y, Zr, I, Pb, Th). A principal component analysis (PCA) with
312 a variance-covariance matrix was performed on the selected elements with the software package
313 PAST 4.1.1 ([Hammer et al., 2001](#)). Contents of the 10 most abundant mineral phases and the most
314 significant grain-size endmembers (EM) were included as supplementary variables.

315 *3.4.5. Pollen analyses*

316 A total of 10 samples throughout core PAR-1 were tested for their pollen contents. Palynological anal-
317 yses were performed on 2 ml of dry sediment using standard pollen extraction techniques ([Faegri and](#)
318 [Iversen, 1989](#)), including deflocculation with KOH, treatment with HCL and HF to extract carbonates
319 and silica, respectively, and acetolysis to extract organic matter. In addition, the samples were reacted
320 with sodium pyrophosphate to deflocculate clays ([Heuser & Stock 1984](#)). Subsequently, the samples
321 were ultrasonicated to remove smaller impurities. Before chemical treatment, 2 *Lycopodium* tablets
322 were added to the samples to calculate concentration and pollen influx ([Stockmarr, 1971](#)). Subsamples
323 were taken to check pollen content before and after ultrasound treatment. The samples were exam-
324 ined under an optical microscope at 400x and 1000x magnification.

325 *3.4.6. Diatom and phytolith analyses*

326 Silicified biological remains, including diatoms and phytoliths, were analysed on 10 selected 2 cm-
327 samples along the core profile of PAR1. The sample preparation was modified after [Piperno \(2006\)](#). In
328 a first step, 5 g of dry sediment of each sample was wet-sieved at 10 and 250 µm to remove sand as

329 well as fine silt and clay. Subsequently, samples were treated with hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂, 30 %) in
330 a water bath at 80°C for 24 h and washed with distilled water by centrifugation (2 min, 900 x g). Silic-
331 ified remains were purified by density separation using zinc iodide (ZnI₂, 2.3 g/ml), followed by wash-
332 ing with distilled water and centrifugation (2 min, 900 x g). Polystyrene microspheres (5 µm diameter)
333 were added as exotic markers for the estimation of absolute abundance data (valves g⁻¹) (Battarbee
334 and Kneen, 1982). Permanent slides were prepared following Renberg (1990) using Naphrax® mount-
335 ing medium (Brunel Microscopes, UK). Examination of the slides was conducted by light microscopy
336 with a Nikon Eclipse E600 microscope equipped with a plan apochromat 100× objective (N.A. 1.32)
337 and differential interference contrast optics (Nomarski). Raw skeleton counts for each diatom taxa
338 were normalized to the total percentage abundances of diatoms.

339 The identification of diatom species was performed according to Krammer and Lange-Bertalot (2000-
340 2006), Lange-Bertalot (2000-2016), and Hoffman et al. (2011), as well as region-specific references
341 (Frenguelli, 1929; Frenguelli, 1936; Hustedt, 1927; Rumrich et al., 2000; Servant-Vildary, 1978;
342 Servant-Vildary and Blanco, 1984). Diatoms were grouped into main ecological groups according to
343 their biological lifestyle/habitat: planktonic, benthic, and aerophilic. Ecological information was mainly
344 drawn from van Dam et al. (1994) and Vos and Wolf (2007), complemented by regional studies of
345 Cumming and Smol (1993), Denys (1991), Servant-Vildary and Roux (1990), Servant-Vildary and Mello
346 e Sousa (1993), and especially Servant-Vildary et al. (2000). Phytolith counting was performed accord-
347 ing to Piperno (2001; 2006). Phytolith morphometries were compared with standard catalogues
348 (Piperno, 2006) and with a phytolith reference collection of selected modern plants from the Atacama
349 Desert (Vargas-Machuca et al., *subm*).

350 3.4.7. Lipid biomarker analyses

351 Lipid biomarkers (*n*-alkanes, fatty acids/phospholipid fatty acids (PLFAs)) were analysed on the 10
352 large-volume bulk sediment samples from the PAR-1 core to characterize the origin of organic matter
353 (OM). Total lipids were sequentially extracted from ca. 45 g of bulk sediment by repeated ultrasoni-
354 cation using a mixture of MQ water (40 ml), methanol (MeOH), and dichloromethane (DCM; 2:1, v/v)
355 following the procedure modified after Bligh (1959). Subsequently, the solvent extracts were collected
356 in a separatory funnel and DCM and MQ water were added (1:1, v/v) for phase separation. The organic
357 phases were removed and the water phases re-extracted twice with DCM. Finally, the bulk solvent
358 was removed by rotary evaporation under vacuum to yield the total lipid extract (TLE). The TLE was
359 subjected to base hydrolysis using 0.5 M aqueous potassium hydroxide (KOH) at 80°C for 2 h to cleave
360 ester-linked fatty acid membrane lipids. After water addition, the neutral lipids (non-saponifiable frac-
361 tion) were first recovered using *n*-hexane. Neutral lipids were subsequently separated into apolar (*n*-
362 alkanes) and polar fractions by silica gel column chromatography (SiO₂, deactivated with 1% H₂O, 60 Å)

363 and eluting with *n*-hexane and DCM:MeOH (1:1, v:v), respectively. The remaining aqueous solution
364 was acidified with concentrated HCl to pH 1 and the fatty acids were extracted with DCM. The total
365 fatty acid pool (including free fatty acids and PLFAs) was transesterified with methanolic HCl (95:5,
366 v/v) to form fatty acid methyl esters (FAMES). The latter were further purified over a SiO₂-Na₂SO₄
367 column with DCM:*n*-hexane (2:1, v:v).

368 *n*-Alkanes were analysed using a gas chromatograph fitted with an on-column injector and flame ion-
369 isation detector (GC-FID; HP 5890). A fused silica capillary column (Agilent DB-5MS; 50 m x 0.2 mm,
370 film thickness: 0.33 μm) was used with He as carrier gas. Samples were injected at 70°C and the GC
371 oven temperature was subsequently raised to 150°C at a rate of 20°C min⁻¹, and then at 6°C min⁻¹ to
372 320°C, which was held for 40 min. FAMES were analysed using an Agilent 7890B GC -FID (DB-5MS
373 column; 50 m x 0.2 mm, film thickness: 0.33 μm). The temperature program used was: 40°C (hold for
374 2 min), ramp to 140°C with 10°C min⁻¹ and to 320°C with 3°C min⁻¹ (hold for 28 min). Both *n*-alkanes
375 and FAMES were quantified against authentic external standard solutions.

376 The average chain length (ACL) and carbon preference index (CPI) of the *n*-alkanes were calculated to
377 characterize the quality of organic matter, with lower values pointing to enhanced degradation or
378 input of petrogenic sources. ACL describes the relative distribution of odd-carbon-numbered higher
379 plant *n*-alkanes (C₂₃-C₃₃) to distinguish between different vegetation types ([Bush and McInerney, 2013](#);
380 [Eglinton and Eglinton, 2008](#)) and is calculated based on the formula:

$$381 \quad \text{ACL}_{23-33} = \Sigma(\text{C}_n \times n) / \Sigma(n),$$

382 where C_n is the abundance of each *n*-alkane with *n* carbon atoms for chain lengths between C₂₃ and
383 C₃₃.

384 The CPI captures the odd over even chain length distribution of *n*-alkanes ([Bray and Evans, 1961](#)) and
385 is calculated with the formula:

$$386 \quad \text{CPI}_{23-33} = 0.5 \times [(\Sigma \text{ even} / \Sigma \text{ odd}) + (\Sigma \text{ even} / \Sigma \text{ odd})]$$

387

388 3.4.8. Chronostratigraphical analyses

389 To achieve chronological information from the PAR1 sediment core, we chose a dating approach ap-
390 plying Accelerator Mass Spectrometry (AMS) radiocarbon (¹⁴C) dating on different sediment fractions
391 as well as Optically Stimulated Luminescence (OSL) dating.

392 AMS ¹⁴C dating was conducted on a woody plant fragment from the sediment surface, on bulk car-
393 bonates (n=2), and on the TLE fraction of bulk sediment (n=10). The wood and carbonate samples
394 were dated at the CologneAMS facility (Germany) after pre-treatment according to the Acid-Alkali-
395 Acid (AAA) extraction and hydrolysis protocols ([Rethemeyer et al., 2019](#)). For TLE AMS ¹⁴C dating, the

396 TLE fractions were transferred into tin elemental analyser (EA) capsules with DCM, and the solvent
397 was slowly removed on a hot plate before wrapping the sample. All samples were measured as CO₂
398 using an elemental analyser interface coupled to a gas ion source-equipped Mini-Carbon Dating Sys-
399 tem (MICADAS) at the Laboratory of Ion Beam Physics of the ETH Zurich, Switzerland (McIntyre et al.,
400 2017; Ruff et al., 2010). Radiocarbon dates were calibrated using OxCal v. 4.4.4 (Bronk Ramsey, 2009;
401 Bronk Ramsey, 2021) applying the SHCal20 calibration curve (Hogg et al., 2020).

402 The sediment intervals from from 0.96 – 0.87 cm and 1.84 – 1.76 cm depths were sampled under
403 subdued red light for luminescence dating in the Cologne Luminescence Laboratory (CLL). Subse-
404 quently, the samples were pre-treated following standard procedures (sieving; HCl 10%, H₂O₂ 10%,
405 and sodium oxalate to remove carbonates, organics and clay, respectively; density separation with
406 sodium polytungstate (SPT) to separate the fraction <2.58 g/cm³) to extract the coarse grain (100-150
407 µm) potassium feldspar fraction.

408 Equivalent dose measurements were performed following the post-IR₂₂₅ protocol (Buylaert et al.,
409 2009). The measurements were done on 1 mm-aliquots (n = 15-26 per sample) that were fixed on
410 steel discs using a Risø TL/OSL reader with a ⁹⁰Sr/⁹⁰Y beta source delivering ca. 0.11 Gy per second at
411 the sample position. OSL signals were stimulated with infrared LEDs and detected through an inter-
412 ference filter with peak transmission at 410 nm. Protocol validation for the PAR samples was done
413 through dose recovery experiments and residual dose measurements (3 aliquots per sample, signal
414 resetting for 24 hours in a solar simulator), which yielded mean dose recovery ratios of 0.92±0.03 (PAR
415 1-1) and 0.90±0.03 (PAR 1-2) and residual doses of less than 3 Gy that equals to less than 2% of natural
416 dose.

417 Equivalent dose distributions of the two PAR-1 samples show a low dose scatter with an over-disper-
418 sion (OD) of 15% for sample PAR 1-1 and a moderate dose scatter with 36% OD for PAR 1-2. Thus, the
419 central age model (Galbraith et al., 1999) was used for burial-dose calculation of PAR1-1, whereas the
420 minimum age model (MAM) was chosen for PAR 1-2 (Galbraith et al., 1999). Fading measurements
421 according to Auclair et al. (2003) resulted in a low mean g-value of 1.2 ± 1.0 %/decade; thus, a fading
422 correction of the post-IR₂₂₅ ages was not applied. Dosimetry of the samples is based on radionuclide
423 concentrations (U, Th, K) as derived from high-resolution gamma spectrometry measured VKTA Ros-
424 sendorf, Germany. Dose rate and age calculations were conducted using the DRAC software (Durcan
425 et al., 2015) based on the measured dosimetry, estimated water contents of 5 ± 5%, empirical K con-
426 tents of 10 ± 2% (Smedley et al., 2012), and cosmic dose rates calculated according to Prescott and
427 Hutton (1994).

428

429 4. Results and Discussion

430 4.1. Precipitation events and subsequent desiccation

431 From the WRF_{era5}-model output for the interval 1990-2020, we extracted a precipitation time-series
432 for the four grid cells covering the catchment of the PARAC_P. The time-series yield numerous small-
433 amplitude rain events during the 30-year interval. Only 14 (respective 5) larger-scale rain events >5
434 mm (>20 mm) occurred with calculated recurrence intervals of 2.14 (6) years (Fig. 2; Suppl. Table S1).
435 These values are lower than recurrence intervals of 10-15 years at the PARAC_P location for events >20
436 mm determined by [Walk et al. \(2020\)](#) based on a coarser-resolution WRF-model run (10-km resolu-
437 tion). Three of the five >20-mm events belong to the winter rainfall cluster typical of the study area
438 ([Reyers et al., 2021](#)), and all five occurred during El Niño events (Fig. 2).

439 Amongst the 14 events with rain >5 mm modelled for the PARAC_P, the August 2006 (29/08/2006) event
440 caused a total rain sum of 39.0 mm, followed by the events in June 2017 (07/06/2017; 33.5 mm), June
441 1991 (18/06/1991; 23.7 mm), and February 2019 (02-09/02/2019; 22.7 mm). In Antofagasta (Fig. 1),
442 the June 1991 event produced 42 mm of total rain within 3 hours ([Garreaud and Rutllant, 1996](#)) and
443 caused massive landslides ([Vargas et al., 2000](#); [Vargas et al., 2006](#)). This specific event also heavily
444 affected the interior desert around Baquedano (17.5 mm) and Aguas Verdes (33.5 mm; [Pfeiffer et al.,](#)
445 [2021](#); Fig. 1; Suppl. Fig. S5). In contrast, the March 2015 event (23-26/03/2015), which was called a
446 “century-scale rain event” by [Pfeiffer et al. \(2021\)](#), yielded a rain sum of only 21.8 mm at PARAC_P over
447 a period of approx. 50 hours. The data of the PARAC_P (Fig. 2) and PARAOBS (Suppl. Fig. S2) time series,
448 but also those of the weather stations at Taltal and Aguas Verdes (Suppl. Fig. S5), show strong varia-
449 tions in the amplitudes of the single rain events, which points to a pronounced spatial heterogeneity
450 in the rain intensities. Thus, the PARAC_P rain signal has to be regarded as a local signal and can only be
451 extrapolated within a very limited spatial range. One recent rain event (05/02/2023) falls beyond the
452 time range of the WRF_{era5} model experiment. This event was recorded by the Chipana weather station
453 just next to PARAC_P, although summing up to only 2.9 mm of rain within approx. 5 hours.

454 Real-colour satellite images of the 14 events with precipitation of >5 mm and the February 2023 rain
455 event illustrate that only 8 of these events led to significant surface modifications in the clay pan. Only
456 for four events >20 mm (June 1991, August 2006, March 2015, June 2017) the satellite images indicate
457 open water bodies (Fig. 3). Surprisingly, no modification was recorded for the February 2019 event
458 (22.7 mm). The existence of open water ponds was confirmed by calculated MNDWI values (Suppl.

Fig. 3: Real-color satellite images of the $PARA_{CP}$ after 8 major rain events. Green and blue polygons highlight the mapped wet spots and open water ponds, respectively. The numbers in brackets give the time lags (in hours) between the end of the last rain (t_0) and the recovery of the satellite images. Please note that satellite images marked 'PS' are pansharpended using the panchromatic band.

459 Fig. S6) and field observations just after the 2015 event (Fernandez-Martinez et al., 2019) that re-
 460 vealed shallow ponds with highly turbid sediment-laden water (Suppl. Fig. S4B). This indicates that
 461 these ponds originate from surface run-off from the drainages rather than pure precipitation on the
 462 clay-pan surface. For the other four events that don't exhibit open water bodies, the surface of the
 463 $PARA_{CP}$ shows a rather homogeneous darker colour, which points to wet spots due to direct precipi-
 464 tation rather than a directional flow.

465 On the images taken after the June 1991 ($t=191$ h after event) and August 2006 ($t=5$ h after event)
 466 events (Fig. 3), water ponds mostly accumulated in the deepest parts of the pan, filling approx. 13.7%
 467 ($43,539 \text{ m}^2$; 8781 m^3) and 27.7% ($88,247 \text{ m}^2$; $21,218 \text{ m}^3$) of the surface area, respectively. After the
 468 March 2015 ($t=65$ h, $81,073 \text{ m}^2$; $17,847 \text{ m}^3$) and June 2017 events ($t=18$ h; $203,789 \text{ m}^2$; $117,085 \text{ m}^3$),

Fig. 2: Timeseries of WRF_{era5} -derived daily rain sum averaged over the four grid cells covering the $PARA_{CP}$ (1990-2020; blue bars) and rain data from Chipana weather station at $PARA_{CP}$ (Nov. 2021- recent; red bars) with major rain events highlighted. The curve in the back shows the Oceanic Niño Index (ONI; NOAA, 2023), with values <0 (filled in blue) indicating La Niña and values >0 (filled in red) indicating El Niño conditions.

469 open ponds covered 25.4% and 63.9% of the clay pan surface area, respectively, with a stronger focus
 470 in the eastern part of the clay pan. This points to a predominant inflow from easterly tributaries.
 471 Deeper insights into the desiccation following a rain event are provided by a time-series of 12 pictures
 472 recorded after the 2017 event (Suppl. Fig. S7). The images show a progressive reduction of the ponds
 473 until final disappearance after ca. 350 hours. The comparison of the images also illustrates ponds
 474 turned into wet spots before complete desiccation. Remaining wet spots finally disappeared 21 days
 475 (ca. 450 h) after the end of the rain event.
 476 The results of the mapping approach are, however, biased by the different time lags between the end
 477 of the last rain (t_0) and the recovery of the satellite images, especially for the early events with poorer
 478 image coverage. To compensate for this time lag, an empirical desiccation function was developed
 479 based on the data of the June 2017 event and applied also to the other three inflow events to predict
 480 the surface areas and volumes for the timing of the last rain t_0 (Suppl. Figs. S8; See supplement for a
 481 detailed description of the used approach).
 482 Calculated areas and volumes at time t_0 for the 1991, 2006, 2015, and 2017 events are given in Table
 483 1. The results suggest that open-water area and volume were largest during the 1991 event and
 484 smallest during the 2006 event. For the 2015 event, we predict values comparable to the 2017 event.

Table 1: Estimated surface areas and volumes for the time t_0 , WRF_{era5}-derived rain sums and average rain rates as well as observed maximum rain rate for the 4 rain events with visible water bodies in PARAC_p. Maximum rain rates (averaged over 1 hour) are from ¹Garreaud and Rutllant (1996) and ²HATPRO rain sensor at

Event	Area open water t_0		Volume open water t_0 m ³	WRF Rain sum PARAC _p	WRF rain rate mm/h	Observed rain rate mm/h
	m ²	%				
18/06/1991	728,314.45	228.5	240,940.15	23.7	7.9	24.0 ¹
29/08/2006	94,936.77	29.8	23,120.99	39.0	4.9	-
24-26/03/2015	212,214.06	66.6	55,319.04	21.8	1.6	15.4 ²
07/06/2017	240,050.60	75.3	95,980.46	33.5	2.8	16.7 ²

485

486 **4.2. Modern vs. Pleistocene precipitation intensities**

487 Comparative modelling experiments of the modern (WRF_{hist}) and LGM conditions (WRF_{LGM}) as ana-
 488 logues for the Late Pleistocene exhibit only a slight change in the rain frequencies but much higher
 489 rainfall amplitudes over the $PARA_{CP}$ and at $PARA_{OBS}$ during the LGM (Fig. 4). Within the modelled 25-
 490 year intervals, the LGM simulation yield approx. 8-9 times more >20 mm events at both sites (Table
 491 2), and more than 10 times more of the heavy >30 and >50 mm events. Consequently, recurrence
 492 intervals for the LGM events are significantly shorter than during the historic interval. Even rainfall

Fig. 4: Percentile-percentile plots of the WRF_{LGM} vs. WRF_{hist} -derived (A) full year, (B) austral autumn (MAM), and austral winter (JJA) daily precipitation sums during the precipitation events modelled for the 25-year study intervals.

493 events exceeding 70 mm that are not modelled for the WRF_{hist} experiment, are predicted by the LGM
 494 run. Furthermore, the LGM events show a distinct change in the seasonality of the rainfall events with
 495 a clear dominance of autumn and winter rain (Figs. 4A and B). These findings are in accordance with
 496 an earlier study (Reyers and Shao, 2019) that found up to 50% more COL in their LGM model run
 497 compared to historic and pre-industrial simulations, mainly during the winter season. Based on the
 498 higher frequency of COL, Reyers and Shao (2019) postulate distinctly different wind statistics and
 499 moisture supply in the Atacama Desert during the LGM.

500

Table 2: Rain frequencies (bold) and recurrence intervals (in brackets) beyond a certain threshold in a 25 years time-interval over the Paranal clay pan ($PARA_{CP}$) and ESO observatory ($PARA_{OBS}$) for the WRF_{hist} and WRF_{LGM} model runs.

Precipitation threshold	$PARA_{CP}$		$PARA_{OBS}$	
	HIST	LGM	HIST	LGM
>10 mm	23 (1.09 yr)	91 (0.27 yr)	15 (1.67 yr)	76 (0.33 yr)
>20 mm	7 (3.57 yr)	56 (0.45 yr)	6 (4.17 yr)	52 (0.48 yr)
>30 mm	2 (12.5 yr)	35 (0.71 yr)	3 (8.33 yr)	30 (0.83 yr)
>50 mm	1 (25.0 yr)	11 (2.27 yr)	1 (25.0 yr)	13 (1.92 yr)
>70 mm	0	5 (5.0 yr)	0	3 (8.33 yr)

501 **4.3. Sediment composition of core PAR-1**

502 **4.3.1. Lithology and grain-size composition**

503 The near-surface sediments of the Paranal clay pan down to 1.88 m depth are generally dominated by
504 clastic particles and lack any obvious traces of organic matter or carbonate remains. Grain sizes vary
505 from clay to gravel in variable contents, with distributions in the sediment samples unveiling three
506 distinct end-members (EM; Fig. 4) that can be traced back to three depositional modes.

507 The fine-grained EM1 has a well-sorted peak with the 10th (P10) and 90th percentiles (P90) of 0.86 and
508 12.66 μm , respectively, and a modal value of 4.88 μm , thus indicating a low-energy deposition. EM1
509 strongly resembles the grain-size distribution of flood deposits from the 2017 rain event (dashed black
510 in Fig. 4A).

511 The medium-grained EM2 consists of well-sorted medium to coarse silt (P10: 1.66 μm ; P90: 62.07 μm)
512 with a mode of 19.79 μm . Such well-sorted silt could be transported both by fluvial/alluvial or aeolian
513 processes (Stuut and Lamy, 2004). Grain-size studies of aeolian dust from the Atacama are sparse (e.g.,
514 Flores-Aqueveque et al., 2014), and their comparability is biased by heterogeneous wind patterns at
515 different sites as well as different sampling methods. Published grain-size data of aeolian sediments
516 from the coastal Pampa de Mejillones exhibit modal grain sizes $>40 \mu\text{m}$ (Flores-Aqueveque et al.,
517 2014), which is significantly larger than EM2. Although maximum wind velocities at Pampa de Mejil-
518 lones are in a similar range (see Suppl. Fig. S1 for comparison), the Mejillones site exhibits different
519 soil characteristics (i.e., easily erodible loose sand and gravel) and only limited soil crusts (Flores-
520 Aqueveque et al., 2010). Furthermore, the used BSNE samplers only recover the vertical aeolian com-
521 ponent mainly transported by saltation (Goossens and Offer, 2000). Dust samples collected at three
522 Coastal Cordillera sites with the MDC, in contrast, rather represent the horizontal aeolian component
523 representative for distal dust and is slightly finer (P10: 1.13-1.29 μm ; P90: 25.77-76.34 μm ; mode:
524 10.30-13.62 μm) and better sorted than EM2 (dashed green lines in Fig. 4A). Although being located
525 further to the north and regularly influenced by local fog due to their lower elevations (695-1179 m
526 asl), the dust sampling sites exhibit a wind circulation pattern (Hoffmeister, 2018) and sulphate soil
527 crust (Voigt et al., 2020) comparable to the PARAC_P site. Based on the coarser grain size and worse
528 sorting of EM2 we conclude that aeolian depositions play only a minor role in the formation of EM2.

529 The predominantly coarse-grained EM3 shows a bimodal distribution (P10: 3.23 μm ; P90: 552.56 μm)
530 with the larger peak ranging from coarse silt to coarse sand (mode: 269.5 μm). Whilst the fine-grained
531 part resembles EM1 and thus probably suggests some re-working of modern flood deposits, the size
532 distribution of the coarse component is in good agreement with those of surface samples from local

Fig. 4: (A) Grain-size distributions of PAR-1 sediment samples (thin gray lines) with EM1 (blue), EM2 (red), and EM3 (yellow) together with drainage samples from the major inlets (dashed light gray), distal dust from the Coastal Cordillera (dashed green), and a sample of the 2017 flood deposits (dashed black); (B) picture of open ponds with sediment-loaded water on 05/04/2015 (10 days after the 2015 flood) surrounded by freshly desiccated areas with desiccation cracks (picture kindly provided by David Wettergreen); (C) major inlet channel of the PARAC_p draining parts of the Sierra Vicuña Mackenna mountain range (in the background); white arrows highlight shrubs of *Calandrinia cf. salsoloides* (picture by Volker Wennrich).

533 inlet streams feeding the clay pan (dashed grey in Figs. 4A, C), which implies some sort of fluvial origin
 534 of EM3. Sand-sized deposits are very abundant in the surroundings of PARAC_p, often concentrated in
 535 the channels draining the local alluvial fans towards the clay pan (Fig. 4C), whereas the surrounding
 536 slopes are mainly covered by gravels, presumably due to the deflation of finer sediments. However,
 537 as the grain size of EM3 also overlaps with proximal coarse aeolian dust from the Atacama (Flores-
 538 Aqueveque et al., 2014), we cannot fully exclude an aeolian sediment supply.

539 Based on its visual characteristics, the 1.88-m long PAR-1 core can be sub-divided into four major
 540 sedimentary facies. The lower section of the core (1.88 - 0.95 m) shows an alternation of facies 1 and
 541 facies 2. Facies 1 consists of a light brown and poorly sorted sandy silt (facies I; Suppl. Fig. S9) with up
 542 to 24.1% of gravel (Fig. 5). The grain-size distribution of facies I is marked by strong fluctuations, with
 543 variable contents of EM2 and coarse EM3 (up to 88%) below 1.15 m indicating significant fluvial input.
 544 In ephemeral drainages on alluvial fans of the Atacama Desert, episodic intense rainfall events cause
 545 stream activation with high water and sediment run-off (Aguilar et al., 2020) that usually occurs as

546 debris-flows/mudflows or overland flow (e.g., Mather & Hartley, 2005; Pfeiffer et al., 2021; Roldán et al., 2022). The very poor sorting, the variable coarse grain size, and the high gravel content of facies I
 547 point to a deposition by distal channelized mudflows or debris-flows from the adjacent alluvial fans.
 548 In the vicinity of the PAR_{CP}, small-scale debris-flows triggered by the March 2015 event were observed (Pfeiffer et al., 2021), and remnants of larger past debris-flow are preserved as block fields at the edges of the modern clay pan surface (Suppl. Fig. S10).
 551
 552 Above 1.15 m depth, the grain-sizes decrease, as visible in a gradual replacement of EM3 by EM1.
 553 Facies I is intercalated by 4 up to 5-cm thick darker horizons of facies II (Suppl. Fig. S9). Elevated contents of EM2 indicate that facies II is slightly more fine-grained than facies I, which points to a reduction in transport energy due to the cessation of the run-off.
 554
 555 The upper core section (0.95 m – top) is much finer is characterized by an alternation of facies III and IV. Facies III is mainly of beige colour and consists of powdery poorly sorted clayey silt (Suppl. Fig. S9).
 557 In contrast to facies I and II, facies III lacks any gravel and exhibits only traces of sand (<5%). These

Fig. 5: Sediment facies, grain-size map, contents of end-members (EM) 2 and 3, gravel and PCA-derived principal component 2 (PC2), magnetic susceptibility (MS) and Zr/Rb ratio, total sulfur (TS) counts as well as total inorganic carbon (TIC) and PC1 and PC3 contents of core PAR-1 vs. depth.

559 deposits are very similar to the surface sediments described from other clay pans in the Atacama De-
560 sert ([Diederich et al., 2020](#); [Ritter et al., 2019](#)). EM analyses reveal that sediments of facies III are
561 mainly composed of low-energy EM1 (up to 100%) with minor contributions of EM2. Interestingly, in
562 some intervals of facies III the sediment appears to be slightly more compact and breaks into cm-sized
563 chips that have a mm- to sub-mm thick lamination. These chips are assumed to be relicts of ancient
564 desiccation cracks similar to those on the modern clay-pan surface (see Fig. 4B). Based on the similarity
565 in the grain-size distribution to the 2017 rain sample and its fine lamination, we assume that EM1 (and
566 so facies III) can be linked to the fine-grained background sedimentation in the clay pan from sus-
567 pended sediment inflow during >20 mm-rain events similar to the four historic ones. Based on the
568 rather good sorting and the fine grain size, we interpret facies III as distal deposits of overland flows
569 or as the fine-grained endmember of mudflows or debris-flows triggered by torrential rain events.
570 Overland flows are typical phenomena in the hyperarid part of the Atacama Desert (e.g., [Amundson](#)
571 [et al., 2012](#); [Owen et al., 2011](#)) and are also observed during the March 2015 rainfall ([Wilcox et al.,](#)
572 [2015](#); [Pfeiffer et al., 2021](#)). During rainfall events, fine sediment is mobilized from adjacent fan sur-
573 faces through winnowing ([Blair and McPherson, 2009](#)). Due to their high threshold velocities for wind
574 erosion ([Shahabinejad et al., 2019](#)), the highly cohesive clay and silt-rich deposits of facies III impede
575 significant aeolian erosion, but rather work as a seal to protect the surface from being deflated.
576 Facies III is evenly intersected by 7 distinct layers of facies IV that are darker in colour, have a thickness
577 of up to 5.5 cm, and show a massive internal structure with relatively sharp lower contacts to the
578 bracketing deposits of facies III. Deposits of facies IV dominantly consist of well-sorted medium to
579 coarse silt attributed to EM2, with minor contents of EM1 and only two layers (0.56-0.52 m, 0.15-0.1
580 m depth) bearing significant amounts of sandy EM3. Due to their limited thickness, sharp basal bound-
581 ary, and coarser grain size, facies IV is interpreted as high-energy equivalent of facies III. The grain-size
582 map (Fig. 5) reveals a characteristic fining-upward grading of facies III deposits just above these event
583 layers, which indicates a common formation. Thereby, facies IV represents the basal section of more
584 energetic overland flows, whereas facies III represents the associated upper low-energetic equivalent
585 deposited after the major flood or during less intense overland flows. The overall higher thickness of
586 facies III compared to facies IV indicates that in contrast to facies IV, facies III horizons were presum-
587 ably not deposited during single events but rather consist of multiple amalgamated events, whose
588 coarse basal parts didn't reach the coring site.

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590
591
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593 4.3.2. Geochemical and mineralogical composition

594 The PCA yielded that 98.0% of the variance in the geochemical composition of the PARAC_P sediments
 595 can be explained by variations in only three components (Fig. 6B). Principle component (PC) 1 has
 596 strong positive loadings of Si and Al and high negative loadings of Ca and S (Fig. 6A), whereas the
 597 loadings of most other elements are less significant. The good correlation of high negative PC1 load-
 598 ings with gypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) as a supplementary variable suggests that PC1 mainly describes vari-
 599 ations in gypsum precipitation vs. siliciclastic deposition. The downcore distribution of PC1 exhibits
 600 high-amplitude fluctuation with generally negative scores in facies I and II, but more homogeneous
 601 low positive values in facies III and IV (Fig. 5). Strong negative peaks of PC1 scores in samples 63/ 64
 602 and, to a lesser amount, in 74/75 point to discrete gypsum layers at 1.38-1.34 m and 1.60-1.56 m
 603 depth, respectively, with maximum XRD-derived gypsum concentrations up to 28.9%. Gypsum precip-
 604 itation in a coarse-grained environment, as documented for facies I and II, is unlikely to have happened
 605 in a lacustrine or salar environment, especially since the gypsum does not form discrete layers in the
 606 core but is rather mixed with detrital material. Therefore, a pedogenic origin of the gypsum, as also
 607 observed in the Huara and PAG clay pans (Diederich et al., 2020; Ritter et al., 2019), is more likely. The
 608 source of gypsum in the Paranal clay pan is, however, not as straightforward as for the other clay pans,
 609 as a primary atmospheric sulphate deposition from coastal fog is mainly blocked by the Coastal cliff
 610 (Wang et al., 2014; Voigt et al., 2020). For the PARAC_P at 2,200 m altitude, atmospheric deposition of
 611 secondary atmospheric sulphate typical for the high Coastal Cordillera (Klipsch et al., 2023) is much
 612 more likely.

Fig. 6: (A) PCA-derived principal components (PC) 1 vs. 2 of the EDXRF-based elemental composition with 10 most abundant mineral phases and grain-size endmembers as supplementary variables. Whereas PC1 is interpreted to show siliciclastic (>0) vs sulphate components (<0), PC2 represents coarser (+) vs. finer (-) grain sizes; (B) explained eigenvalues of the PCs vs. number of PCs.

613 Beyond the gypsum dominance, high loadings of Ca might also be partly attributed to calcite (CaCO_3),
614 as visible in the moderate correlation with PC1 (Fig. 6A). Due to its low content $\leq 3.2\%$, calcite detection
615 by XRD is less accurate. In the TIC contents, which are directly linked to the appearance of carbonates,
616 two distinct peaks are however visible between 1.20 - 1.08 m and between 1.80 - 1.74 m depth that
617 point to calcite enrichments. As a detrital origin of the calcite in PAR-1 is unlikely due to the absence
618 of carbonaceous bedrock in the catchment, a formation from carbonaceous rhizoliths by plant roots
619 (Diederich et al., 2020; Jordan et al., 2014) is regarded as the likely calcite source. Both the formation
620 of pedogenic gypsum and of rhizoliths, however, require soil formation and thus indicate a discontin-
621 uous sedimentation.

622 PC2 explains 17.5% of the variance in the element composition of the PAR-1 record and is character-
623 ized by high positive loadings of Si, Ca, and Na (Fig. 6A), which yield a strong correlation with quartz
624 (SiO_2), albite $\text{Na}(\text{AlSi}_3\text{O}_8)$, and microcline $\text{K}(\text{AlSi}_3\text{O}_8)$. The former minerals were also identified in the
625 sediments of the PAR_{CP} by a previous study (Fernandez-Martinez et al., 2019) and are common sili-
626 cate minerals in Atacama soils, e.g., at the nearby Yungay site (Ewing et al., 2006; Sutter et al., 2007).
627 High negative loadings of Mg and moderate negative values of Fe and Al correlate with anorthite
628 ($\text{Ca}(\text{Al}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_8)$) and the phyllosilicates muscovite ($\text{KAl}_2(\text{AlSi}_3\text{O}_{10})(\text{OH})_2$), vermiculite
629 ($(\text{Mg,Fe,Al})_3(\text{Al,Si})_4\text{O}_{10}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$), and kaolinite ($\text{Al}_2(\text{Si}_2\text{O}_5)(\text{OH})_4$) (Fig. 6A). Simultaneous correla-
630 tion of grain-size EM1 and EM3 with negative and positive loadings of PC2, respectively, are a clear
631 indication of a grain-size dependency of PC2, with positive values pointing to coarse and negative
632 values to fine-grained samples.

633 PC3, which only explains 1.5% of the total variance, is marked by high positive loadings of Fe that
634 correlate with magnesio-hornblende ($\text{Ca}_2(\text{Mg}_4\text{Al})(\text{Si}_7\text{Al})\text{O}_{22}(\text{OH})_2$) and EM2 (Fig. 6A). The downcore dis-
635 tribution reveal a strong resemblance of peaks in PC3 with the peaks in the Zr/Rb ratio and the mag-
636 netic susceptibility (MS) in facies I and II. High values in Zr/Rb ratio and MS are usually linked to coarser
637 grain sizes (Diederich et al., 2020; Ritter et al., 2019).

638 4.3.3. Biological indicators

639 As mentioned before, the sediments of core PAR-1 lack any macroscopic organic remains. Palynolog-
640 ical analyses reveal that all samples are barren of pollen or other palynomorphs except for three pollen
641 grains.

642 In contrast, all investigated samples from core PAR-1 ($n=10$) possess diatoms, with the diatom flora
643 comprising 32 different taxa (see Suppl. Fig. S11 for the full diatom diagram). Diatom concentrations
644 are extremely low, comparable to other clay pans in the Atacama Desert (Ritter et al., 2019), but ex-

645 habit a progressive trend from levels <10 valves *g⁻¹ in the core section below 1.0 m depth to a maxi-
 646 mum concentration of 61 valves *g⁻¹ at approx. 0.20 m depth (Fig. 7). Higher diatom concentrations
 647 in facies III and IV can be traced back to enhanced diatom growth, although we cannot exclude less
 648 clastic dilution due to a decrease in the clastic sedimentation rate as a potential reason. Assigned
 649 diatom habitats (i.e., aerophilous, benthos, plankton) illustrate a change in diatom assemblages along
 650 the profile, with predominantly aerophilous species in the facies I and II below 1.3 m depth that are
 651 progressively replaced by benthic species above, whereas planktonic contents remain relatively con-
 652 stant. Aerophilic diatoms are described from various subaerial or terrestrial habitats (Johansen, 2010)
 653 and are characterized by their ability to survive complete desiccation. Consequently, lower aerophilic
 654 diatom concentrations in the sediments of to PARA_{CP} compared to clay pans further north, in the hy-
 655 per-arid core of the Atacama (Diederich et al., 2020; Ritter et al., 2019), presumably are due to lower
 656 precipitation at the latter sites. The predominant occurrence of aerophilics in the lower section of core
 657 PAR-1 rather point to the presence of only very shallow ephemeral water bodies. Some aerophilic
 658 diatoms species, like *Denticula elegans* as most abundant species in the lower core section, were also
 659 observed in desert soil crusts (e.g., Johansen et al., 1984). The increasing numbers in non-aerophilic
 660 (benthic + planktonic) diatoms with a maximum of 98.9% at approx. 0.20 m depth indicate a stronger
 661 influence of stagnant but still highly energetic waters in facies III and IV. A similar trend is also visible

Fig. 7: Downcore variations of diatom habitats, diatom salinity affinity (light blue - oligosaline to freshwater, medium blue – mesosaline, dark blue – polysaline), diatom and phytolith concentrations, n-alkane and PLFA concentrations, n-alkane average chain length (ACL), carbon preference index (CPI), and percentages of short (C₁₇₋₁₉), medium (C₂₃₋₂₅), and long-chained n-alkanes (C₂₇₋₃₃) of the total n-alkane fraction. (for legend of the sediment facies see Fig. 5).

662 in the salinity affinities of the diatom assemblages with a transition from (poly-)hypersaline conditions
663 (18 - 69 ‰ salinity) to more mesohaline to oligohaline (<0.18 -18 ‰ salinity).

664 Besides diatoms, the sediments possess also plant phytoliths as traces of terrestrial vegetation in the
665 catchment of the PAR_{CP}. Phytolith concentrations behave similar to diatoms concentrations, with
666 values <1 phytoliths *g⁻¹ in facies I and II below 1.0 m depth and a constant increase to its maximum
667 of 56.4 phytoliths *g⁻¹ in the surface samples (Fig. 7). As diatoms and phytoliths display contrary signals
668 of aquatic vs. terrestrial flora, the parallel trend of upcore increasing concentrations seems to be ra-
669 ther caused by a reduction in detrital dilution due to a decreasing sedimentation rate. Most of the
670 identified phytoliths in the PAR-1 core are unfortunately not taxonomically diagnostic, except for sin-
671 gle trilobate and polylobate morphotypes that can be assigned to the Arundinoideae and Pooideae
672 sub-families of the Poaceae, respectively (Vargas-Machuca et al., *subm*). A recent study on phytoliths
673 in modern plants from the Atacama Desert, however, has shown that amongst the investigated plant
674 families only species of Poaceae and Bromeliaceae produce siliceous phytoliths, and thus phytoliths
675 underestimate the real vegetation cover (Vargas-Machuca et al., *subm*). Nevertheless, the phytolith
676 in the sediments of PAR1 are a strong indication for some sort of grassy vegetation in the Paranal
677 catchment, that is lacking today.

678 Although very low TOC values ≤0.1% throughout the entire PAR-1 record reflect extremely low organic
679 matter contents, lipid biomarkers preserved in the sediment shed light into past vegetation changes
680 of the study site. Lipid biomarker analyses yield higher abundances of *n*-alkanes (71-430 ng g⁻¹ dry
681 weight [DW]) and PLFAs (199-1847 ng g⁻¹ DW; Fig. 7; Suppl. Table S2) compared to sediments from
682 the Aroma transect (Knief et al., 2020) and Yungay site (Wilhelm et al., 2017) in the hyperarid core of
683 the Atacama (Sites 5 and 7 in Fig. 1A). On the other hand, the PAR-1 sediments show *n*-alkane con-
684 centrations similar to soils in the Paposito transect at altitudes >2000 m (Mörchen et al., 2021; site 7 in
685 Fig. 1A) or in a fossil *Tillandsia* dune north of the Rio Loa (Jaeschke et al., 2023). Total *n*-alkane and
686 PLFAs concentrations in the PAR-1 core vary with depth, with higher values of >200 and >800 ng g⁻¹
687 DW, respectively, in facies I and II. Only the lowermost sample from the base of the sediment se-
688 quence exhibits lower values. In facies III and IV, above 1.0 m depth, concentrations of both *n*-alkane
689 and PLFAs are significantly lower but increase towards (Fig. 7).

690 *n*-alkanes in the PAR_{CP} record are dominated by odd-numbered homologues ranging from C₁₇ to C₃₄
691 with an ACL ranging from 26.3 and 29.9 (average ACL 28.2), thereby pointing to higher proportions of
692 long-chained *n*-alkanes derived from higher plants. Relatively low carbon preference indices (CPI) be-
693 tween 1.5 and 5.7 (average CPI 2.8) imply a high to moderate degree of organic matter degradation
694 (Bray and Evans, 1961). According to the *n*-alkane-based discrimination scheme by Mörchen et al.
695 (2021), all PAR-1 samples clearly plot into the rain-affected cluster. Except for the lowermost sample

696 from the base of the core, the chain-length distribution of the *n*-alkanes in facies I and II below 0.9 m
 697 depth shows only a minor contribution of short-chained homologues <C₂₀ indicative of algae/bacteria,
 698 but a preference of medium chain lengths of C₂₃₋₂₅ rather indicative for submerged plants (Bush and
 699 McInerney, 2013) and an additional maximum in long-chained homologues >C₂₉ (Fig. 7). In the upper
 700 samples, in contrast, long-chained *n*-alkanes (C₂₉ - C₃₁) become dominant, whereas medium chain
 701 lengths gradually drop. Algae-derived C₁₇₋₁₉ *n*-alkanes exhibit a remarkable rise between 0.6 and 0.4 m
 702 depth and remain high towards the top of the sediment succession. The uppermost sample yields a
 703 more uniform chain-length distribution.

704 These obvious shifts in the chain-length pattern of the *n*-alkanes along the core can be attributed to
 705 changes in the proportions of submerged to higher plants (Bush and McInerney, 2013). A preferential
 706 degradation effect on the different homologues cannot fully be excluded, however, the parallel trends
 707 of increasing diatom valve concentrations, which are not affected by organic matter degradation, and
 708 concentrations of algae-indicating C₁₇₋₁₉ *n*-alkanes towards the top of the core (Fig. 7) rather exclude
 709 significant decay.

710 4.3.4. Chronology

711 The development of a robust age-depth model for clay pay sediment records in these desert environ-
 712 ments is challenging (e.g., Diederich et al., 2020; Nienhaus et al., 2023; Ritter et al., 2019), e.g., due to
 713 the scarcity of vegetation and resulting plant remains and the discontinuous deposition. The chronol-
 714 ogy of the PAR-1 core was determined using a combination of AMS radiocarbon dating of different
 715 sediment fractions and OSL dating.

716 Two OSL samples from the bottom parts of the two core segments yielded uncorrected post-IR₂₂₅ IRSL
 717 ages of 7.9 ± 0.5 ka (PAR 1-1; 95.5-86.5 cm depth) and 31.6 ± 4.5 ka (PAR 1-2; 184-175.5 cm depth;

Table 2: Results of the OSL dating

Sample	Lab-ID	Depth (cm)	n	Environmental dose rate (Gy/ka)	Over-dis-persion (%)	Burial dose (Gy)	g-value (%/dec)	Age (ka)
PAR 1-1	C-L5460	95.5-86.5	15	5.2 ± 0.3	15 ± 3	41.0 ± 1.6 (CAM)	1.2 ± 1.0	7.9 ± 0.5 (CAM)
PAR 1-2	C-L5461	184-175.5	26	5.0 ± 0.3	36 ± 5	159 ± 21 (MAM)	1.2 ± 1.0	31.6 ± 4.5 (MAM)

718 Table 2). Due to a low dose scatter and good performance of CAM, the determined age for sample
 719 PAR 1-1 is considered as reliable. Sample PAR 1-2, however, is more complex to interpret due to the
 720 rather large scatter of the dose rates that seems to display two separate populations of 38.1 ± 2.8 and

721 71.5 ± 5.4 ka. The resulting CAM age of 54.0 ± 4.8 ka may thus overestimate the true burial age. There-
 722 fore, we used the minimum age model instead, which yields an age of 31.6 ± 4.5 ka for sample PAR 1-
 723 2.

724 The only plant-derived AMS ¹⁴C-date (COL6183; Table 3) was measured on a wooden plant macro re-
 725 main of an undetermined terrestrial plant (likely cf. *Calandrinia* sp.) sampled from the clay pan surface
 726 at the eastern edge of the playa, where similar stems can be frequently found in-situ (Suppl. Fig. S12).
 727 The plant macro remain was ¹⁴C-dated to 439 cal yr BP – modern, although with a rather large 2σ
 728 uncertainty of the calendar age due to a broad plateau in the SHCal20 calibration curve (Hogg et al.,
 729 2020). This indicates a subrecent surface age of the PAR_{CP}, which, in contrast to other investigated
 730 clay pans in the Atacama and Namib deserts (Diederich et al., 2020; Nienhaus et al., 2023; Ritter et al.,
 731 2019), argues against significant deflation or a hiatus at the surface.

732 Two ¹⁴C analyses on the bulk sedimentary inorganic carbon (COL6188, COL6189) provided ages of
 733 27,519 ± 123 and 33,398 ± 520 cal yr BP at depth of 1.13 and 1.77 m depth. While the upper carbonate
 734 ¹⁴C age (COL6188) of 27,519 ± 123 cal yr BP significantly overestimates the adjacent OSL age of sample
 735 PAR 1-1, the lower carbonate sample (COL6189) matches the minimum age model estimate for OSL
 736 sample PAR 1-2 within the (1σ) uncertainties (Fig. 8). Similar over/underestimations of carbonate ¹⁴C

Table 3: AMS ¹⁴C dating results from core PAR-1; for F¹⁴C see (Reimer et al., 2004); δ¹³C measured with AMS, not comparable to stable isotope ratio-MS measurement due to different isotopic fractionation; calendar ages calibrated with OxCal v. 4.4.4 (Bronk Ramsey, 2021), Calibration curve: SHCal20 (Hogg et al., 2020)

Lab-ID	depth (cm)	C (μg)	¹⁴ C age (yr BP)	+/-	δ ¹³ C (‰)	mean cal age (yr cal BP)	SD (2σ)	sample material
COL6183	surface	988	249	42	-13.8	221	221	wood
COL6188	113.0	913	23,324	131	6.8	27,519	123	bulk carbonate IC
COL6189	177.0	541	29,037	351	11.9	33,398	520	bulk carbonate IC
COL6190	185.9	1000	12,448	66	-31.6	14,560	207	TLE
COL6191	97.3	1000	16,160	80	-33.4	19,445	115	TLE
COL7438	28.0	162	11,715	109	-26.4	13,553	120	TLE
COL7440	49.5	275	10,921	103	-28.4	12,857	96	TLE
COL7441	61.3	247	13,366	118	-26.7	16,035	178	TLE
COL7444	105.0	640	17,535	161	-25.7	21,185	244	TLE
COL7446	125.0	341	15,656	137	-24.7	18,923	144	TLE
COL7447	135.0	612	16,118	143	-25.5	19,396	186	TLE
COL7449	155.0	562	13,781	127	-25.8	16,660	201	TLE
COL7450	166.5	693	16,523	154	-28.5	19,910	209	TLE

737 ages are a common feature also in other sites of the Atacama Desert and Altiplano and have been
738 attributed to reservoir effects, contribution of old catchment carbonates, and residence time of dis-
739 solved inorganic carbon in groundwater (Diederich et al., 2020; Geyh et al., 1999; Herrera et al., 2018;
740 Placzek et al., 2006).

741 In total 10 ¹⁴C ages were derived from the TLE fraction of bulk sediments taken from depths between
742 0.2 m and 1.89 m at the bottom of the core (Table 3). The obtained ages range between 12,857 ± 96
743 cal yr BP and 21,185 ± 244 cal yr BP, however, without a concordant age-depth relationship. Ages from
744 the upper core section <1.05 m increase with depth, with a minor age-reversal at 0.5 m depth. Extrap-
745 olating these ages towards the top of the core suggests a surface age of approx. 8000 – 10,000 cal yr
746 BP, which contradicts the sub-recent age interpreted from the plant ¹⁴C age. Furthermore, the TLE ¹⁴C
747 ages significantly overestimate the OSL age from a depth of ca. 0.9 m by approx. 11,000 years. In the
748 lower section >1.05 m depth, the TLE-derived ages do not exhibit any increasing trend with increasing
749 depth, but rather cluster between 14,560 ± 207 and 19,910 ± 209 cal yr BP with the youngest age at
750 the bottom of the core (Fig. 8). The cores exhibit a clear vertical stratification without any signs of
751 post-sedimentary or drilling-induced mixing (Suppl. Fig. S9), and samples were carefully checked for
752 potential contamination (Rethemeyer et al., 2019), e.g., by liner plastic. We thus exclude drilling-arti-
753 facts or lab contamination with old C, but also a major influence of haloturbation (Sager et al., 2021)
754 known from other places in the Atacama (e.g., Zinelabedin et al., *subm.*).

755 A similar irregular ¹⁴C (there reported as Δ¹⁴C) profile is also described from the Yungay soil profile in
756 the hyperarid core, approx. 50 km north of PAR_{CP} (Ewing et al., 2008; no. 5 in Fig. 1A), and is explained
757 by long OC residence times >10,000 years in the soil and downward OC transport during heavy rain
758 events. Such effects could also have occurred at the PAR_{CP}. On the other hand, the irregular TLE ¹⁴C
759 ages throughout the PAR-1 core might also be caused by repeated activation of soil microbial commu-
760 nities due to infiltration of rainwater during flood events, which utilize a major proportion of fossil
761 carbon (Ziolkowski et al., 2013). A similarly high bacterial activity in the PAR-1 sediments is indicated
762 by high PLFA concentrations (Suppl. Table S2). The available TLE ¹⁴C ages, however, don't allow any
763 further estimates, e.g., on the timing of bacterial activity.

764 Since carbonate and TLE ¹⁴C dating produced uncertain ages that cannot be validated within this study,
765 we don't include them in the age-depth model. As a consequence, we built an age-depth relationship
766 for the PAR-1 core only on the plant ¹⁴C age at the surface and the OSL ages of 7.9 ± 0.5 ka at ca. 0.91

Fig. 8: Age-depth data of core PAR-1. Red diamonds illustrate postIR₂₂₅ IRSL ages, yellow stars TLE ¹⁴C ages, green triangle ¹⁴C age on plant macro remain of *cf. Calandrinia sp.*, pink triangle ¹⁴C ages on bulk carbonate inorganic carbon. Black horizontal and vertical bars mark the 2σ (OSL: 1σ) dating uncertainties and sample thickness, respectively.

767 m depth and 31.6 ± 4.5 (MAM) at ca. 1.80 m. This hampers the interpretation of high-resolution
 768 changes, but at least enables to interpret the lower facies I and II as pre-Holocene (i.e., Late Pleisto-
 769 cene) and the upper facies III and IV as of Holocene age.
 770

771 5. Interpretation

772 Despite the limited chronological constraints, the available proxy data of pilot core PAR-1 from the
 773 PARAC_P shed new light on the precipitation variability in the Coastal Cordillera of the Atacama Desert
 774 since the Late Pleistocene. The study of historic rain events as ground truthing and sensitivity test
 775 furthermore enables to draw conclusions on the amplitudes of rain events in the geological past.

776 5.1. Sensitivity of the Paranal clay pan to historic rain events

777 As mentioned earlier, during the past 30 years only four heavy rain events with rain sums >20 mm
 778 caused significant surface run-off and subsequent water and sediment inflow into the Paranal clay
 779 pan. This indicates that a certain threshold of approx. 20 mm needs to be exceeded to trigger surface
 780 run-off on the surrounding hillslopes and in the drainage system and subsequently form open-water

781 bodies in the clay pan. Hillslopes in the catchment of the clay pan are dominantly covered by Ca-
 782 sulfate dust and crust (*chusca*; Álvarez et al., 2016) with very high infiltration capacities (Pfeiffer et al.,
 783 2021). During lower amplitude precipitation events, this Ca-sulphate cover absorbs much of the pre-
 784 cipitation, and thus, hampers surface run-off (Griffiths et al., 2012; Jordan et al., 2015; May et al.,
 785 2020; Ritter et al., 2022) and erosion (Ritter et al., 2023, Mohren et al., 2020). Significant surface and
 786 overland flow and activation of the local drainages obviously only occur during high-amplitude events
 787 with rain sums >20 mm, when this critical infiltration threshold is exceeded. Our empirically deter-
 788 mined threshold of ≈ 20 mm is lower than thresholds between 25 and 99 mm of rain previously re-
 789 ported for overland flows on hillslopes in the study area (Pfeiffer et al., 2021). This bias might be
 790 caused by a general slight underestimation of the WRF_{era5}-simulated rain-sums (see supplement), but
 791 also due to the site-specific conditions of the PARACP, with its amphitheatre-like steep catchment. The
 792 exclusive occurrence of these flood events during El Niño years, on the other hand, strongly implies a
 793 high sensitivity of surface run-off in the catchment of PARACP to El Niño conditions, which, in turn,
 794 points to an ENSO-modulation of the Paranal sediment signal.

795 Predicted volumes of the four events, however, do not correlate with the WRF_{era5} model-derived rain
 796 sums (Fig. 9A). The 1991 event with a rain sum of only 23.7 mm yields by far the largest volume of
 797 240,940 m³, whereas the lowest volume of 23,121 m³ is estimated for the 2006 event with the highest
 798 rain sum of 39.0 mm. Calculated volumes for the 2015 (21.8 mm) and 2017 (33.5 mm) events of 55,319
 799 m³ and 95,980 m³, respectively, plot between these extreme values. This random clustering of pre-
 800 dicted volumes vs. rain sums clearly indicates that the water inflow into the clay pan and thus the
 801 amplitude of surface run-off is not primarily dependent on the total rain amount.

Fig. 9: Reconstructed open water volume for 4 flood events plotted (A) vs WRF_{era5}-derived rain sums, (B) vs. WRF_{era5}-derived average and observed maximum rain rates

802 If plotted against the rain rate (averaged over the duration of the event as well as the maximum rain
803 rate), the open water volumes show no obvious linear dependency (Fig. 9B). Of the four events, the
804 2006 event forms a distinct outlier with a much lower reconstructed water volume for the given aver-
805 age rain rate. Unfortunately, observational rain-rate data for the 2006 event are not available in a
806 sufficient temporal resolution to confirm the WRF-derived rain rate. As the duration of this event
807 could only be estimated from a newspaper article², we cannot exclude an underestimation of the du-
808 ration and thus an overestimation of the calculated average rain rate for the 2006 event. Aside from
809 the 2006 event, calculated open-water volumes of the other three >20 mm events follow a fairly linear
810 trend with both average and maximum rain rates (Fig. 9B). This suggests that, once the rain sum ex-
811 ceeds the infiltration threshold of the surface soil, the amount of surface run-off is primarily triggered
812 by the rain rate.

813 Maximum rain rates (1 hour average) determined at the PARA_{OBS} reached up to 15.4 and 16.7 mm/h
814 for the 2015 and 2017 events, respectively, with short-term peaks of up to 42 mm/h (Pfeiffer et al.,
815 2021). Up to 24 mm/h (1 hour average) were measured in Antofagasta during the 1991 event, which
816 is regarded as the highest rate in the last century (Garreaud and Rutllant, 1996). Nevertheless, even
817 these maximum values are far below average infiltration rates for Atacama soils between 78 and 244
818 mm/h that need to be exceeded to produce infiltration-excess overland flow (Pfeiffer et al., 2021). On
819 the other hand, the WRF-derived rain sums for the >20mm events are at the lower limit required for
820 saturation-excess run-off between 25-99 mm (Pfeiffer et al.; 2021). This implies that run-off thresholds
821 in the Atacama vary on local scales and that at least in the catchment of the PARA_{CP} soils are much
822 more susceptible to rainfall events than previously expected. Moreover, the four captured flood
823 events in the studied interval of 30 years suggest a recurrence interval of those run-off events of 7.5
824 years, which is lower than published values derived from modelling experiments (Walk et al., 2020).
825 This finding has significant implications, for instance for hazard assessment and the prediction of fu-
826 ture heavy rain-induced floods (Ministerio del Medio Ambiente, 2020).

827 **5.2. Holocene precipitation variability**

828 Unfortunately, the available chronological information from the PAR-1 core only allows to discrimi-
829 nate between the Late Pleistocene and Holocene parts of the record, thereby hampering the inter-
830 pretation of higher-resolution precipitation fluctuations during the past millennia. The majority of the
831 Holocene core section consists of clayey silt of facies III, which shows a strong similarity to the deposit
832 of the 2017 event (Fig. 4). We therefore interpret facies III deposits as ‘background’ sedimentation
833 that were accumulated in the clay pan during run-off events with >20 mm of rain, comparable to the

² <https://www.mch.cl/2006/08/30/sorpresiva-y-fuerte-lluvia-dejo-mas-del-mil-afectados-en-antofagasta/>

834 four observed historic events. These run-off events apparently caused open ponds in the clay pan that
835 persisted for several weeks (maybe months) before complete desiccation. The dominance of benthic
836 and planktonic diatoms along with the higher diatom and algae-indicating C₁₇₋₁₉ *n*-alkane concentra-
837 tions, especially above ca. 0.5 m depth (Fig. 10), suggest that these ponds existed long enough to be
838 repeatedly colonized by diatoms (and presumably also other algae). Salinity affinities of the diatoms
839 (i.a., *Aulacoseira ambigua*, *Hyalodiscus schmidtii*, *Navicula minima*, *Sellaphora atomoides*) indicate oligo-
840 saline to fresh-water conditions in these ponds (Fig. 10, Supp. Fig. S11), which points to a precipi-
841 tation rather than groundwater-origin of the ponds. Grass phytoliths and higher concentrations of C₂₇₋
842 ₃₃ *n*-alkanes (Fig. 7) suggest a certain kind of vegetation cover with grasses in the PARAC_P catchment
843 that is almost completely barren today.

844 Calculated sedimentation rates the facies III are very low. Taken the total thickness of facies III of 74.9
845 cm and a basal age of 7.5 to 10 kyr, the mean sedimentation rate is in the order of 74.9- 99.8 mm/kyr.
846 If we assume mean recurrence intervals for the Holocene >20 mm rainfall events of 7.5 to 10 years
847 (100-133 events per kyr) similar to the historic period, mean sedimentation rates for the events are in
848 the order of 0.56 to 1 mm/event, which confirms the amalgamated nature of facies III.

849 Many regional paleoclimate records indicate a very dry Early to Middle Holocene. Paleowetland de-
850 posits from Salar de Punta Negra (ca. 110 km to the east of PARAC_P; no. 2 in Fig. 1A) experienced a
851 change to a phreatic playa after 9.7 cal kyr BP, before sedimentation ceased sometime in the Early
852 Holocene due to a major lowering of the local water table (Quade et al., 2008; Fig. 10). Also, lake-
853 levels at Laguna Miscanti (23°44'S, 67°46'W, 4140 m; no. 4 in Fig. 1A) dropped significantly after 9 cal
854 kyr BP (Grosjean et al., 2001; Fig. 10). Moreover, at Sierra de Varas, approx. 110 km to the southeast
855 of the PARAC_P (site 1 in Fig. 1A), the cessation of paleowetland deposition and the accumulation of
856 amalgamated alluvial fans during the Early to Middle Holocene were interpreted as an indication of a
857 long-term arid period between 9.5 and 4.7 cal kyr BP, with only debris-flow deposition caused by low-
858 frequency torrential rain events (Sáez et al., 2016). The pronounced aridity during the Early Holocene
859 is linked to reduced ENSO activity (e.g., Moy et al., 2002; González-Pinilla et al., 2021) and is even
860 postulated as a potential reason for the abandonment of human settlements (López Mendoza et al.,
861 2022). Lake-level reconstructions (e.g., Bobst et al., 2001; Grosjean et al., 2001; Fig. 10) as well as
862 pollen and macro remains from rodent middens, e.g., from Lomas de Tilocalar (de Porras et al., 2017)
863 indicate that the overall aridity was interrupted by a short Middle Holocene pulse with moderately
864 wetter conditions than present between 6-5 kyrs BP. Due to the limitations of the paleo records, how-
865 ever, the climatology of this wet pulse cannot be resolved in the PAR-1 core.

Fig. 10: Selected proxies of the PAR-1 record vs. depth plotted next to Late Pleistocene to Holocene records from the Atacama Desert: reconstructed mean annual rainfall anomalies from rodent middens (González-Pinilla et al., 2021), water-table reconstructions from paleowetland deposits (Quade et al., 2008), and reconstructed lake-level variations of Laguna Miscanti (Grosjean et al., 2001) over the past 16,000 cal yr BP. The two grey bars highlight the Central Atacama Pluvial Events (CAPE) I and II (Quade et al., 2008).

866 During the Late Holocene, groundwater-discharge deposits at Sierra de Varas, which accumulated af-
 867 ter 4.7 cal kyr BP, point to a period of continuous spring activity due to an increase in precipitation
 868 (Sáez et al., 2016) that coincides with an increase in ENSO activity after 5 cal yrs BP (Moy et al., 2002).
 869 Synchronously, lake levels of Laguna Miscanti almost returned to pre-Holocene values (Grosjean et
 870 al., 2001; Fig. 10). Plant macrofossils and pollen assemblages of fossil rodent middens from the nearby
 871 sites in the Coastal Cordillera illustrate a general gap in the Early to Middle Holocene due to an arid
 872 phase, but a moisture increase after 3.7 kyrs BP (Maldonado et al., 2005; Díaz et al., 2012). High-
 873 resolution reconstructions from faecal pellets yield a generally higher than present mean annual rain-
 874 fall during the Late Holocene, however, with high decadal-scale variability (González-Pinilla et al.,
 875 2021). Although chronologically uncertain, the increase in diatom and phytolith concentrations in the
 876 PAR-1 core above 0.5 m depth along with the rise in algae-indicating *n*-alkanes might be associated
 877 with a shift to more frequent or heavier precipitation in the Paranal area during the Late Holocene.
 878 The seven particularly coarse-grained layers of facies IV with their sharp upper and lower boundaries
 879 and thicknesses of up to 5.5 cm point to recurrent extreme flood events in the Paranal catchment
 880 during the past 7.5 to 10 ka. Based on their sedimentological characteristics we assume that the in-
 881 tensity of these extreme flood events was significantly higher than during the more frequent floods
 882 that have led to the Holocene background sedimentation of facies III, i.e., they significantly exceeded
 883 the historic rain sums and rates of max. 39 mm and 24 mm/h, respectively. Following Pfeiffer et al.
 884 (2021), we call them “Millennial-scale rain events”. Taking the basal age of the Holocene section of 8
 885 to 10 kyrs, their mean recurrence interval is in the order of 1070-1430 years, thereby suggesting a

886 sub-orbital forcing. Similar multi-centennial to millennial variations in the Holocene rainfall variability
887 are also observed in rodent middens from the central Atacama Desert (González-Pinilla et al., 2021)
888 and marine records from southern Chile (Lamy et al., 2001), and are explained by tele-connections to
889 North Atlantic Bond events and/or latitudinal shifts of the Southern Westerlies, respectively. Due to
890 the poor age control, the major driver of these rainfall maxima within the Holocene sediments of the
891 PAR-1 records cannot be resolved. Furthermore, it has to keep open, whether the more frequent oc-
892 currence of layers in the lower part below 0.5 m depth (n=5; Fig. 10) represents a higher frequency of
893 heavy floods during the Early to Middle Holocene or is the consequence of lower background sedi-
894 mentation rate. In any case, the events may partly be associated with torrential run-off and flood
895 events caused by low-frequency storms, which at Sierra de Varas has caused alluvial fan activation in
896 the Early to Middle Holocene (Sáez et al., 2016), albeit a direct linkage is excluded due to the restricted
897 age control and the strong heterogeneity of heavy rainfall in the Atacama (Reyers et al., 2021).

898 **5.3. Late Pleistocene precipitation history at the Paranal clay pan**

899 The distinct differences in the lithological, geochemical, sedimentological, and mineralogical compo-
900 sition between the pre-Holocene (below ca. 1.0 m depth) and Holocene sediments point to signifi-
901 cantly different transport and depositional processes in the catchment of the PAR_{CP} prior to the Holo-
902 cene, most likely driven by different precipitation patterns. The poor sorting and variable but coarse
903 grain size with high gravel contents of the pre-Holocene sediments suggest a much stronger sediment
904 input from adjacent alluvial fans. Sediment supply presumably took place by proximal mudflows or
905 debris-flows, likely triggered by much stronger torrential rainfall. As visible in the multiple peaks in the
906 magnetic susceptibility, the Zr/Rb ratio, and EM 3 (Figs. 3 and 10), sediment inflow was rather episodic
907 and interrupted by phases of lower transport energy. The interbedded finer layers, however, lack a
908 normal grading as observed for the Holocene coarse layers, which argues against a simple gradual
909 settling from a concentrated suspension after the major mudflow, e.g., in a playa lake. In fact, the
910 intercalation of calcite and gypsum beds in between the coarse strata, the latter reflected by repeated
911 peaks in sulphur (Fig. 10), rather indicates repeated paleo-soil formation between mudflows. The low
912 concentration of diatoms and algae-indicating *n*-alkanes (Fig. 10) can be traced back to the specific
913 mudflow facies, with high fluxes of mobilized soil material from the slopes that heavily dilute the
914 sparse biological traces. Favourable growing conditions for diatoms in such a highly dynamic environ-
915 ment might be limited to short-lived ponds after the major floods. Due to the low sample resolution
916 of the diatom analyses, however, such pond episodes cannot be detected. The most abundant diatom
917 species in the lower core section, *Denticula elegans* (Suppl. Fig. S6), is a typical aerophyllous diatom
918 species (van Dam et al., 1994) with an affinity to polysaline conditions (Diederich et al., 2020). The
919 latter may point to the existence of highly saline ephemeral ponds in the catchment. *Denticula elegans*

920 was, however, also found in desert soil crusts accompanied by other aerophilic diatom species
921 (Johansen et al., 1984). This further supports a formation from re-mobilized soil material by mudflows
922 or debris-flows.

923 The interpreted intensified alluvial fan activity during the Late Pleistocene, however, requires much
924 higher rainfall intensities and rates compared to present-day conditions and even to the “Millennial-
925 scale rain events”. In our WRF_{LGM} modelling experiments, the predicted amplitudes of torrential rain-
926 fall events significantly exceed those of historic rain events, and the recurrence intervals of heavier
927 events are much shorter (see chapter 4.2). Such a significantly higher precipitation in the Atacama
928 Desert and adjacent Precordillera during the Late Pleistocene is widely known from rodent midden
929 (Betancourt et al., 2000; de Porras et al., 2017; Díaz et al., 2012; González-Pinilla et al., 2021; Latorre
930 et al., 2002; Maldonado et al., 2005) and paleowetland records (Quade et al., 2008; Sáez et al., 2016)
931 as well as lacustrine (Grosjean et al., 2001) and marine sediment cores (Lamy et al., 1998; Lamy et al.,
932 2000; Mohtadi et al., 2004; Stuut and Lamy, 2004).

933 Two major wet phases, the so-called Central Atacama Pluvial Events (CAPE), occurred between 17.5-
934 14.2 ka (CAPE I) and 13.8-9.7 ka (CAPE II), separated by a short arid phase (Quade et al., 2008; Fig. 10).
935 A comparison of these Late Pleistocene records, however, suggests noticeable regional differences in
936 the timing, duration, and intensities of the pluvial events (Sáez et al., 2016). Moisture reconstructions
937 based on pollen and faecal pellet suggest CAPE I to have been significantly wetter (González-Pinilla et
938 al., 2021) and driven by both summer and winter precipitation, whereas CAPE II was mainly caused by
939 summer rainfall (Maldonado et al., 2005; Quade et al., 2008).

940 According to our WRF_{LGM} model output, the stronger LGM rainfall events show a strong seasonality
941 with a clear dominance of autumn and winter rainfall. Enhanced winter rain in the southern Atacama
942 Desert during the LGM is linked to a strengthening as well as a northward shift of the Southern
943 Hemisphere westerlies (Lamy et al., 1998; Lamy et al., 2000; Maldonado et al., 2005). On the other
944 hand, the LGM modelling results show a significantly higher number of cut-off lows in the Atacama
945 Desert compared to historic simulations (Reyers and Shao, 2019), which points to different wind
946 statistics and moisture supply in the study area. Based on foraminiferal assemblages of a marine sed-
947 iment core off the Atacama coast (24°01.99'S, 70°49.41'W; 2507 m water depth), Mohtadi et al. (2004)
948 interpreted for the period 16 and 13 kyrs BP an increase in sea-surface temperatures and a weakening
949 of the coastal upwelling. Thus, a marine driver due to higher ocean temperatures cannot be excluded.
950 A direct correlation of the coarse mudflow deposits in the lower part of the PAR-1 core to CAPE I or II
951 (or an older pluvial phase preceding CAPE) is not possible due to the poorly constrained chronology in
952 this part of the core. However, based on the apparent similarities between the PAR-1 record and the
953 water-table variations in paleowetlands (Quade et al., 2008) and the lake-level curve of Laguna

954 Miscanti (Grosjean et al., 2001; Fig. 10), an assignment of these fluvial deposits to the CAPE complex
955 is regarded as highly likely.

956 **5.4. Rainfall projection for the 21st century**

957 The strong variations in the natural precipitation regimes between the LGM and Holocene also raise
958 questions about future rainfall intensities and frequencies under global warming conditions. More
959 frequent heavy rainfall in the Atacama during the last decade might already be seen as a first indicator
960 for a future intensification of precipitation events.

961 Climate projections under the RCP8.5 scenario predict a rise in yearly median temperature of up to 3
962 degree until the end of the 21st century around the Paranal site (Cantalloube et al., 2020). In the south-
963 ern Atacama, total precipitation is projected to simultaneously decrease by 15-40% (Araya-Osses et
964 al., 2020; Ortega et al., 2019). Due to the general warming, mainly during Austral winter (Araya-Osses
965 et al., 2020), the intensity of ENSO-modulated extreme rain events at the coast, however, is projected
966 to increase until 2100 (Ortega et al., 2019).

967 Additional hints on the development of the Atacama rainfall under future global warming are provided
968 by a climate modelling experiment of the Atacama under mid-Pliocene conditions (3.2 Ma; Reyers et
969 al., 2023), a period that is regarded as a potential analogue of a 3°C warmer world in the future. The
970 mid-Pliocene simulation predicts an almost doubling of the annual rainfall for most of the desert south
971 of 20° S, compared to a historic experiment, mainly due to stronger rainfall events during austral win-
972 ter (Reyers et al., 2023). Assuming similar atmospheric dynamics for the future Atacama, the authors
973 conclude that regional rainfall extremes beyond historic observations might occur.

974 Thus, it is rather likely that the study area in the near future will face fewer but stronger winter rain
975 events than the ones observed for the past 30 years. These events may be in the order of the “Millen-
976 nial-scale rain events”, which are repeatedly documented in the Holocene part of the PAR1 record or
977 the even larger events documented in the Late Pleistocene core section.

978 **6. Conclusions**

979 From the combination of multi-disciplinary analyses of a short sediment core from the Paranal clay
980 pan with a ground truthing approach of historic rain events the following conclusions can be drawn
981 concerning the Late Pleistocene, Holocene and modern precipitation variability in the southern Ata-
982 cama Desert.

983

984 i) Satellite imagery of historic rain events of the past ca. 30 years in combination with
985 downscaled climate modelling and meteorological data illustrate that the Paranal clay pan

986 reacts very sensitively to stronger precipitation events. Rain sums >20 mm and simulta-
987 neously high rain rates over the Paranal catchment are required to exceed the high soil
988 infiltration of the surrounding slopes and to generate surface run-off in the catchment.
989 Subsequent inflow of sediment-rich water via the local drainage network results in the
990 formation of open-water ponds in the clay pan.

991 ii) The coincidence of most of these events with El-Niño years points to an ENSO-related
992 driver of heavy rain in this part of the Atacama, likely in combination with cut-off lows and
993 moisture conveyor belts.

994 iii) From the multi-disciplinary study of the 1.88-m long PAR-1 sediment core it has become
995 evident that dating of the clay pan sediments is difficult. However, the chronostratigraphic
996 data in combination with sedimentological, mineralogical, geochemical, and biological
997 analyses provides important information on regional precipitation events and precipita-
998 tion changes on glacial-interglacial as well as millennial timescales.

999 iv) During the Late Pleistocene, enhanced alluvial activity in the PARAC_P catchment is re-
1000 flected in particularly coarse-grained mudflow or debris-flow deposits and probably cor-
1001 related to wetter conditions during the Late Pleistocene CAPE (Central Atacama Pluvial
1002 Events) complex that were postulated for the study area before. In between the mudflow
1003 or debris-flow events, gypsum and calcite-enriched sediments reflect low sedimentation
1004 and paleo-soil formation.

1005 v) During the Holocene, rain events similar to historic ones >20 mm led to fluvial sediment
1006 supply, short-lasting standing water bodies, and fine-grained sedimentation with rates of
1007 <10 cm/kyr or 0.5-1 mm per event. The episodic rain events at least sporadically enabled
1008 higher vegetation with grasses in the presently barren landscape. Recurrent coarse-silt
1009 layers intercalating these Holocene background sediments are traced back to “Millennial
1010 scale rain events” that significantly exceeded the intensity of observed historic events.
1011 The occurrence of these events, which imply precipitation maxima on a sub-orbital time-
1012 scale, has major implication for instance for hazard assessment and the prediction of fu-
1013 ture heavy rain-induced floods in the Atacama.

1014

1015 **Data Availability**

1016 All data of this study will be available at the CRC1211 database (<https://www.crc1211db.uni-ko->
1017 [eln.de](https://www.crc1211db.uni-koeln.de)).

1018

1019

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1039

1040 **Declaration of interest**

1041 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial
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1043

1044 **Author Contributions**

1045 V.W.: project idea, fieldwork, sediment sample preparation, sample measurement & data evaluation,
1046 manuscript writing.; C.B.: meteorological data evaluation, manuscript reviewing and editing; D.B.: OSL
1047 dating and data evaluation, manuscript reviewing and editing; R.C.: diatom and phytolith analysis,
1048 manuscript reviewing and editing; D.H.: satellite imagery and remote sensing, meteorological data,
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1050 ing and editing; F.K. & J.H.S.: meteorological data, manuscript reviewing and editing; A.M.: pollen
1051 analyses, manuscript reviewing and editing; L.O.: remote sensing, manuscript reviewing and editing;
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1056

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1559 **Supplementary Material**

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1561 **Site information**

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Fig. S1: Wind data of the “Chipana” weather station collected over the period 27/11/2021 - 19/10/2023, with data gaps between March 2022 – December 2022 and June 2023 – October 2023. A) Wind rose of the collected wind data illustrating the dominant wind directions and velocities. B) Wind velocities plotted vs. day time to illustrate the diurnal wind cycle with sunrise around 11UTC and sunset around 23UTC. The color coding reflects the frequency of occurrence of specific wind velocities and directions. Lines indicate percentiles per wind direction (A) and hour (B), respectively, with median (thick, solid) upper and lower quartile (dashed) 1%- and 99%-percentile (dotted, thick) and min and max (dotted, thin.)

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1564 **Material and methods**

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1566 **Validation of the WRF-derived precipitation data**

1567 WRF_{era5}-derived daily rain sums extracted for the PARA_{OBS} grid cell were validated against the 4.5-years
1568 precipitation time series (01/11/2014 – 28/02/2019) measured at the ESO VLT observatory (see meth-
1569 ods chapter of the main text). Both datasets show an overall good match, both in the occurrence of

Fig. S2: Daily rain sums (in mm) over the grid cell of the ESO VLT observatory (PARA_{OBS}) for the time interval 01/11/2014 – 28/02/2019 derived from the WRF_{era5} simulation experiment (blue bars) plotted against daily rain sums recorded by the rain sensor of the LHAATPRO installed at the PARA_{OBS} (red bars).

1570 the rain events, but also in their relative amplitudes (Fig. S1). The direct comparison, however, yields
1571 a systematic underestimation of the WRF-derived precipitation sums compared to the weather station
1572 data. Thus, the WRF data for the $PARA_{CP}$ are considered as minimum values.

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1574 Validation of the WRF-derived precipitation data

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Fig. S3: Percentile-percentile plots of the WRF_{era5} vs. WRF_{hist} -derived full-year daily precipitation sums during the precipitation events modelled for the 25-year study intervals.

1577 Field work

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Fig. S4: Images of the sampling site of the 2017 event sample. A) Artificial pit dug on 06/04/15, 11 days after the March 2015 event, just at the edge of the open pond (picture kindly provided by David Wettergreen). The suspension-rich shallow water is visible at the right side of the image. The pit was originally 80 cm deep. B) Picture of the same pit taken on 29/01/22, almost completely filled with sediment of the 2017 rainfall event (length of the white scales is 10 cm; picture by Volker Wennrich). The 2017 event sample was taken from the surface of the left round depression.

1579 **Results and Discussion**

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1581 **Precipitation events and subsequent desiccation**

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Fig. S5: Daily rain sums (in mm) for the interval 1990-2019 from the weather stations in Aguas Verdes (25°25'04\"S; 69°57'45\"W; 1560 m above sea level (asl)) and Taltal (25°24'13\"S; 70°28'47\"W; 36 m asl)

Fig. S6: Real-color satellite images of the PARAC_p after the June 1991, August 2006, and June 2017 rain events (upper row) with mapped wet spots (green polygons) and open water ponds (blue polygons), and overlain with MNDWI values (lower row). The numbers in brackets give the empirically determined threshold values of the MNDWI values.

1583 **Open water area and volume calculation**

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1585 To evaluate the effect of desiccation on ponds and moist areas in the clay pan over time, and to back
1586 calculate the initial extend of the water bodies at t_0 , a test study of the interval after the June 2017
1587 event (d_1 - d_{18}) was performed that is covered by 12 satellite images recorded with an average temporal
1588 resolution of 41 hours (Fig. S7).

Fig. S7: Series of real-color satellite images of the $PARA_{CP}$ recorded during an approx. 20 days interval after the the June 2017 rain event. Green and blue polygons highlight the mapped wet spots and open water ponds, respectively. The numbers in brackets give the time lags (in hours) between the end of the last rain (t_0) and the recovery of the satellite images. Please note that satellite images marked 'PS' are pansharpened using the panchromatic band.

1589 Figure S8 shows the surface areas and volumes of open water bodies in the clay pan vs the time lags
1590 between the end of the rain and image acquisition (in hours), respectively. The data of the 2017 event
1591 clearly points to an exponential decrease of the pond surfaces and volumes that is perfectly fit by an
1592 exponential trendline. Based on the exponential trendline, a surface area and volume for t_0 (end of
1593 the rain) of 240,051 m^2 and 95,980 m^3 , respectively, can be calculated. This estimated surface area
1594 corresponds to 75.3% of the total clay pan area, what appears realistic with respect to the size of the
1595 wet area on the satellite image taken on 08/06/2017 (Fig. S7), 18 hours after the end of the rain.

1596 Since comparable satellite imagery time series are lacking for the other events, we assume a similar
 1597 desiccation behaviour, although taking into account that this is a simplification that doesn't consider
 1598 variable evaporation conditions (wind speed, temperature, solar insolation). We then determined the
 1599 time gap between the points of the 1991, 2006, and 2015 events and the corresponding
 1600 areas/volumes on the 2017 reference functions. With this time gap we calculated synthetic
 1601 exponential desiccation curves for the three events (Fig. S8) and subsequently surface areas and
 1602 volumes for t_0 .

1603 The area of 728,314 m² calculated for the 1991 event corresponds to 228.5% of the total clay pan
 1604 surface area (318,781.3 m²). This illustrates the limitation of the surface-area estimates for a filling
 1605 >100%, because the approach assumes an infinite flat surface area and does not consider the bowl-
 1606 shape of the clay pan. The volume estimates, however, are not affected by this limitation, and thus,
 1607 will be used for further discussions.

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Fig. S8: Timeseries of mapped surface area (A) and volume (B) of open-water ponds in the PARACP for the 4 heaviest flood events versus time (in hours) after the end of the rain. The continuous red lines and the statistics refer to the exponential desiccation functions empirically determined for the 2017 event, whereas dashed lines illustrate the predicted desiccation functions for the June 1991 (blue), August 2006 (green), and March 2015 (pink) events.

Fig. S9: Core images and respective sediment facies of the two segments of core PAR1. Please note that no images were available for the bulk core catcher samples (CC) that were taken from the bottom ends of the core segments.

Fig. S10: Boulder field at the southern edge of the PARAC_P as remnant of an old debris-flow, whose fine fraction was subsequently washed out by later rainfall (picture kindly provided by Andreas Vogt).

Fig. S11: Full diatom diagram of core PAR-1 grouped according to the biological lifestyle/habitat. Blue bars indicate planktonic species; green bars benthic, and orange bars aerophilous (Diagram: R. Carballeira).

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Fig. S12: (A) Plant remains in in-situ position in the eastern part of the Paranal clay pan (three exemplary plants are highlighted by red arrows). (B) Close-up of the fossilized remain of cf. Calandrinia sp. that was used for ^{14}C dating. (Pictures: Volker Wennrich).

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Suppl. Table 2: Detailed results of the lipid biomarker analyses of core PAR-1.

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sample ID	depth	facies	PLFA (ng g ⁻¹)						n-alkanes (ng g ⁻¹)					
			sum PLFA (C ₁₂₋₂₀)	sat FA	MUFA	PUFA	Tersat br FA	mid-satbr FA	total n-alkanes (C ₁₇₋₃₄)	C ₁₇₋₁₉	C ₂₃₋₂₅	C ₂₇₋₃₃	ACL C ₂₃₋₃₃	CPI C ₂₃₋₃₃
PAR-1	0-35	III, IV	768.4	512.2	241.3	8.4	8.1	0.7	245.1	19.5	12.2	43.2	28.1	2.4
PAR-2	39-47	III	568.5	374.9	180.9	7.7	6.9	0.7	216.0	23.7	9.5	40.0	28.9	3.1
PAR-3	57-65	III, IV	447.0	300.2	137.4	4.9	6.1	0.6	199.4	7.3	9.0	52.3	29.2	3.4
PAR-4	74-84	III, IV	196.5	149.7	45.0	1.4	2.7	0.2	188.9	7.5	5.4	58.8	29.9	5.7
PAR-5	91-100	I, IV	279.6	193.4	80.7	0.0	3.3	0.5	158.5	9.1	8.9	31.3	28.6	2.6
PAR-6	100-127.5	I, II	877.3	621.8	241.6	7.6	8.7	0.2	418.3	14.5	45.6	69.9	27.7	2.1
PAR-7	127.5-134	I, II	845.5	580.5	250.0	9.2	8.1	0.2	234.6	4.8	19.4	51.6	28.3	2.5
PAR-8	145.5-153.5	I	698.5	480.6	206.7	7.3	5.7	0.2	294.0	9.8	30.8	54.0	27.7	2.6
PAR-9	169.5-177	I, II	1829.1	1294.1	505.8	18.7	16.1	0.4	429.8	6.2	51.0	69.5	27.6	2.0
PAR-10	185.5-192	II	286.4	229.0	51.6	2.2	3.4	1.4	70.7	6.9	5.3	5.9	26.3	1.5

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1639 **sat FA** - general bacteria

1639

1640 **MUFA** - Proteobacteria

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1641 **PUFA** - Fungi

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1642 **tersatbr FA** – Firmicutes

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1643 **mid-satbr FA** - Actinobacteria/Actinomycetes

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1644 **OH-FA** - alteration of PLFAs

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1645 **cyclo FA** - stress/starvation indicator

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1646 **C₁₇₋₁₉ n-alkanes** - algae

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1647 **C₂₃₋₂₅ n-alkanes** - submerged plants

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1648 **C₂₇₋₃₃ n-alkanes** - higher plants

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Suppl. Table 1: List of rain events >5mm over the Paranal clay pan derived from the WRF_{era5}-model with time of the last rain, duration, used satellite images and results (surface area, volume) of the mapping of wet spot and open-water ponds, and WRF-derived rain sums and rates

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Event	last rain (UTC)	duration	comment	satellite	Satellite image acquisition	days	hours	Area wet		Area open water		Volume
								m ²	%	m ²	%	
18/06/91	18/06/91 07:30	3	open water	Landsat 5	26/06/91 06:08	8	190.6	274313.8 m ²	86.1	43539.0 m ²	13.7	
15-17/03/95	17/03/95		no visible water	Landsat 5	18/04/95 13:46	33						
18-22/02/99	22/02/99		no visible water	Landsat 5	24/02/99 00:00	2						
01-02/06/00	COL 02/06/00 13:30	13	wet spots	Landsat 5	02/06/00 14:13	0	0.7					
17-18/02/01			no visible water									
05-07/02/04			no visible water									
11/02/05			no visible water									
18-22/02/05			no visible water									
29/08/06	30/08/06 09:30	8(*)	open water	Landsat 5	30/08/06 14:27	1	4.9	311221.3 m ²	97.6	88247.2 m ²	27.7	
07-09/07/11	COL, AR 09/07/11 07:30		wet spots	Landsat 7	11/07/11 14:30	5	55.0	126711.0 m ²	39.7			
10-16/02/12												
24-26/03/15	COL, MCB 26/03/15 08:30	13.5	open water	Planetscope	28/03/15 14:36	2	54.1	196159.7 m ²	61.5	81073.3 m ²	25.4	
09/08/15	09/08/15 18:30		no visible water	Planetscope								
07/06/17	MCB 07/06/17 21:00	12	open water	Sentinel-2A	08/06/17 14:37	1	17.6	344817.3 m ²	108.2	203789.4 m ²	63.9	
			open water	Planetscope	10/06/17 14:01	3	65.0	317618.3 m ²	99.6	99408.8 m ²	31.2	
			open water	Planetscope	12/06/17 14:02	5	113.0	115444.0 m ²	36.2	43312.0 m ²	13.6	
			open water	Planetscope	13/06/17 14:02	6	137.0	60848.8 m ²	19.1	29211.0 m ²	9.2	
			open water	Planetscope	14/06/17 14:02	7	161.0	36088.0 m ²	11.3	22029.0 m ²	6.9	
			open water	Planetscope	16/06/17 14:02	9	209.0	31158.0 m ²	9.8	9902.0 m ²	3.1	
			open water	Landsat 8	17/06/17 11:15	10	230.3	27471.2 m ²	0.1	-	-	
			open water	Planetscope	19/06/17 14:02	12	281.0	13138.0 m ²	4.1	3206.1 m ²	1.0	
			open water	Sentinel-2A	21/06/17 14:47	14	329.8	7917.0 m ²	2.5	-	-	
			open water	Planetscope	22/06/17 14:02	15	353.0	6523.0 m ²	2.0	1618.7 m ²	0.5	
			wet spots	Planetscope	25/06/17 14:03	18	425.1	1456.0 m ²	0.5			
			no visible water	Planetscope	28/06/17 14:02	21	497.0	0 m ²	0			
02-09/02/19			no visible water									
05/02/23	06/02/23 04:20		wet spots	Planetscope	06/02/23 13:40	0	9.3					

* <https://www.mch.cl/2006/08/30/sorpresiva-y-fuerte-lluvia-dejo-mas-del-mil-afectados-en-antofagasta/>